

Can We Ever Develop an Ideal RNA Force Field? Lessons Learned from Simulations of the UUCG RNA Tetraloop and Other Systems

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ABSTRACT: Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are an important and well-established tool for investigating RNA structural dynamics, but their accuracy relies heavily on the quality of the employed force field (*ff*). In this work, we present a comprehensive evaluation of widely used pair-additive and polarizable RNA *ffs* using the challenging UUCG tetraloop (TL) benchmark system. Extensive standard MD simulations, initiated from the NMR structure of the 14-mer UUCG TL, revealed that most *ffs* did not maintain the native state, instead favoring alternative loop conformations. Notably, three very recent variants of pair-additive *ffs*, OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21, DES-Amber, and OL3_{R2.7} successfully preserved the native structure over a $10 \times 20 \mu\text{s}$ time scale. To further assess these *ffs*, we performed enhanced sampling folding simulations of the shorter 8-mer UUCG TL, starting from the single-stranded conformation. Estimated folding free energies ($\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$) varied significantly among these three *ffs*, with values of 0.0 ± 0.6 , 2.4 ± 0.8 , and 7.4 ± 0.2 kcal/mol for OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21, DES-Amber, and OL3_{R2.7}, respectively. The $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ value predicted by the OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21 *ff* was closest to experimental estimates, ranging from -1.6 to -0.7 kcal/mol. In contrast, the higher $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ values obtained using DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} were unexpected, suggesting that key interactions are inaccurately described in the folded, unfolded, or misfolded ensembles. These discrepancies led us to further test DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} *ffs* on additional RNA and DNA systems, where further performance issues were observed. Our results emphasize the complexity of accurately modeling RNA dynamics and suggest that creating an RNA *ff* capable of reliably performing across a wide range of RNA systems remains extremely challenging. In conclusion, our study provides valuable insights into the capabilities of current RNA *ffs* and highlights key areas for future *ff* development.

INTRODUCTION

Nucleic acid (DNA and RNA) molecules are involved in countless cellular processes, physiological and pathological ones. While DNA forms primarily canonical Watson–Crick double helices, RNA molecules adopt an astonishingly variable spectrum of three-dimensional folds. Many RNA molecules are dynamic, some even disordered, and most RNA molecules interact with diverse proteins in a cellular environment.^{1–5}

Atomistic explicit solvent molecular dynamics (MD) simulations represent a genuine complement of experimental methods in studies of RNA structural dynamics offering very fine spatiotemporal resolution.^{6–12} However, MD simulations also have considerable limitations. First, the accessible time scale of MD simulations is much shorter than the time scale of RNA structural dynamics in most physiological processes. This limitation can, in principle, be overcome by using diverse enhanced sampling simulation techniques,¹³ albeit these techniques bring additional and often significant approximations compared to standard unbiased MD simulations.⁹ Second, and perhaps more importantly, the outcome of RNA

MD simulations critically depends on the capability of an empirical potential, i.e., force field (*ff*), to approximate the potential energy surface of real RNA molecules and their interactions with other molecules.^{9,14–22} Thus, many biochemical processes involving RNA molecules are challenging for MD simulations. Neglecting limits of MD methodology may lead to overinterpretation of the simulation data, especially when only global metrics are reported and true atomistic details of the trajectories are not carefully monitored.²³ Contemporary MD simulations cannot also reliably predict RNA structures.⁹ At present, MD techniques are most powerful when used to complement experimental

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Table 1. List of RNA *ffs*, Water Models, and Ion Parameters Used in MD Simulations

<i>ff</i> label	core <i>ff</i>	subsequent modifications ^a	solvent model	ion parameters
OL3	OL3 ^{28–31}		OPC ⁷⁸	Joung&Cheatham ⁸¹
OL3 _{CP} -gHBfix21 ^b	OL3	CP ⁶⁸ with dihedral refit, ^{16,69} gHBfix21 ⁵⁶	OPC	Joung&Cheatham
OL3 _{CP} -gHBfix _{UNCG19}	OL3	CP with dihedral refit, gHBfix _{UNCG19} , ⁴⁷ NBfix _{0BPh-pur} ⁶³	OPC	Joung&Cheatham
OL3 _{CP} -gHBfix19	OL3	CP with dihedral refit, gHBfix19 ¹⁸	OPC	Joung&Cheatham
OL3 _{CP} -gHBfix19	OL3	CP with dihedral refit, gHBfix19	OPC	charmm22 ⁸³
PAK	OL3	NBfix (RNA–RNA interactions) for O2', ter-O3', ter-O5', <i>pro</i> -R _p , and <i>pro</i> -S _p oxygens ⁶²	OPC	Joung&Cheatham
OL3 _{R2.7}	OL3	NBfix for –CH...O– interactions ⁶¹	OPC	Li&Merz ⁸⁵
DESRES	DESRES ⁴⁴		TIP4P-D ⁷⁹	charmm22
DES-Amber	DES-Amber ⁷²		TIP4P-D	charmm22
ROC	ROC ⁴³		TIP3P ⁸⁰	Joung&Cheatham
ROC	ROC		OPC	Joung&Cheatham
Chen&Garcia	Chen&Garcia ⁷³		TIP3P	Chen&Pappu ⁸⁴
BSFF1	BSFF1 ⁷⁵		TIP3P	Joung&Cheatham
CHARMM36	CHARMM36 ⁷⁷		TIP3P _{CHARMM} ⁷⁶	CHARMM ⁷⁶
CHARMM _{Drude}	CHARMM _{Drude} ^{94–97}		SWM4-NDP ⁹⁸	CHARMM _{Drude}
AMOEBA	AMOEBA ^{60,99}		AMOEBA	AMOEBA

^aAbbreviation CP stands for “Case phosphate” parameters by Steinbrecher et al.⁶⁸ combined with refit of affected dihedral potentials.^{16,69}

^bSimulations run with the original gHBfix_{opt} potential containing modification for sugar donor–sugar acceptor interactions (see *Methods* for explanation).

studies that provide high-quality, atomic-resolution structural data as starting points for simulations.⁹

Assessment of *ff* performance, identification of problems, and attempts to improve the *ffs* is an ongoing process. A genuine approach for (RNA) *ff* improvement is to compare the simulation data with the atomistic experimental structures. The conventional method is to monitor the structural stability of native interactions seen in the respective experimental structures available in the Protein Data Bank (PDB, <https://www.rcsb.org/>).²⁴ However, such analyses may be affected by the static (averaged) nature of the experimental structures and the limited convergence of the simulation trajectories. It is sometimes difficult to separate structural instabilities caused by *ff* inaccuracies from real dynamics, which is masked in the experimental structures due to ensemble averaging. It can be illustrated by the X-ray structure capturing the binding of AU-rich single-stranded RNA (ssRNA) element to the HuR C-terminal RNA recognition motif domain.²⁵ Despite the relatively high nominal resolution of 1.9 Å, the most interesting part of the structure, the RNA binding, was poorly visible in the electron densities. MD simulations helped to determine that the X-ray data arise from a mixture of different RNA binding patterns and registers.²⁵

One of the main issues when parametrizing *ffs* is to ensure that they work satisfactorily over a broad range of RNA systems. Taking into account the structural diversity of RNA, it is an open question whether we can have a single universal *ff* capable of dealing with all kinds of RNA structural dynamics. For example, we have recently carried out the first simulation studies of a spontaneous binding of ssRNAs to RNA-binding protein domains.^{26,27} To simulate the binding process, we had to radically scale down van der Waals interactions (not only base stacking but also sugar–base and sugar–sugar interactions) of the common AMBER RNA OL3^{28–31} *ff*. The *ff* modification called *stafix* prevented spurious ssRNA self-interactions (essentially structural collapse). However, *stafix* is not intended for simulations of structured RNAs.²⁶

In the past decade, a set of short RNA molecules has become a prominent benchmark to analyze the *ff* performance

and to refine the *ffs* with the help of primary experimental data (NMR data or folding free energies).^{15,16,18,19,32–56} One of the key systems is the UUCG tetraloop (TL) which possesses a well-defined native structure with canonical base pairing in the stems and characteristic noncanonical interactions involving sugar-base and base-phosphate (BPh) hydrogen bonds (H-bonds) in the loop.^{15,18,36,41,44,47,50,56–59} For the UUCG TL both unambiguous experimental structure and measured folding free energies are available.^{32–36,57–59}

Common *ff* testing involves validating the overall structural stability of the native interactions during standard MD simulations.^{22,43,60,61} More complicated benchmark setups involve the calculation of folding free energies (and subsequent comparison with experiments) by enhanced sampling simulations. They enable the assessment of not only the structural stability of native conformations but also the balance between the native conformation and the misfolded/unfolded ensembles.^{15,16,18,41,44,50,62,63} The UUCG TL appears at first sight to be an easy target. It does not contain any RNA tertiary interactions (such as A-minor interactions⁶⁴ and other ribose zippers and backbone interactions^{65,66}) which are fundamentally important in larger folded RNAs. Still, RNA *ffs* have been notoriously struggling to match the experimental data for the UUCG tetraloop.^{15,18,41,43,47,63}

In this study, we provide a thorough assessment of the capability of RNA *ffs* to simulate the UUCG TL. Although the UUCG TL is usually included within the benchmark set of testing systems by studies introducing new *ff* variants, it is not uncommon that the testing is done on a limited time scale and/or there is rather superficial structural analysis without convincing evidence that the native state was dominantly sampled. Here, we collected an extended set of standard MD simulations starting from the benchmark 2KOC NMR structure of the 14-mer UUCG TL which includes a canonical stem with five base pairs.³⁶ Altogether, we investigated a set of 16 *ffs* in a series of multiple (typically 10 × 20 μs) MD simulations. Our goal was to compare the behavior of common RNA *ffs* (including polarizable ones) in a structural description of native interactions that define the UUCG native structure.

Our study confirms that the UUCG TL is a challenging system for MD simulations. The majority of the tested *ffs* irreversibly disrupted the native state and preferentially sampled alternative loop conformations. Nevertheless, we identified three very recent RNA *ffs* that provided stable structural descriptions of the UUCG 2KOC 14-mer structure on our time scale. For these *ff* variants, we performed a set of enhanced sampling folding simulations of the shorter 8-mer UUCG TL having a stem with two canonical base pairs. The folding simulations revealed less satisfactory results and striking differences in predicted folding free energies among those *ffs* that performed well in standard simulations of the 14-mer UUCG TL. We then performed additional standard simulations on other nucleic acids (NA) systems for selected *ffs* to better understand their behavior. These simulations also revealed striking differences among the tested *ffs*. Altogether, we report results that are based on ~2.5 ms of standard simulations and ~1.2 ms of enhanced sampling simulations. In summary, our study provides unique insights into the performance of contemporary RNA *ffs* for the structural description of the common UUCG TL benchmark system and unveils important paths for ongoing *ff* development. The results also underline the enormous intricacy of RNA *ff* parametrizations.

METHODS

System Preparation and Simulation Protocols for Pair-Additive *ffs*. For standard simulations, we used the UUCG NMR structure (PDB ID 2KOC; selecting structure #13 which is characterized by the shortest distances of native H-bonds)³⁶ for the preparation of starting topology and coordinates of the *r*(ggcacUUCGgugcc) 14-mer, i.e., the UUCG TL with a stem having five base pairs. We used a smaller *r*(gcUUCGgc) 8-mer for folding simulations, which were initiated from one strand of the A-RNA duplex (see the paragraph about enhanced sampling simulations below).

For standard simulations of the 2KOC structure, we tested 14 different setups with recent pair-additive RNA *ffs* (Table 1). Several variants were prepared based on the common⁶⁷ and widely used *ff99bsc0χ_{OL3}* (i.e., OL3) RNA *ff*.^{28–31} The OL3 *ff* was in some setups further adjusted by the van der Waals (vdW) modification of phosphate oxygens developed by Steinbrecher et al.⁶⁸ in combination with refit of the affected α , γ , δ and ζ torsions parametrized by us.^{16,69} This RNA *ff* version is abbreviated as OL3_{CP} henceforth and the AMBER library file can be found in Supporting Information of ref 16.

We used three variants of general H-bond fix (gHBfix) potentials,¹⁸ i.e., (i) gHBfix19 potential, where all –NH...N–base–base interactions are strengthened by 1.0 kcal/mol and all –OH...bO– and –OH...nbO– sugar–phosphate interactions are weakened by 0.5 kcal/mol,¹⁸ (ii) gHBfix_{UNCG19} version, where –NH...N– and –NH...O– base–base H-bonds are strengthened by 0.5 kcal/mol, sugar–phosphate interactions are weakened by 0.5 kcal/mol, sugar donor–base acceptor H-bonds are strengthened by 0.5 kcal/mol, and base donor–sugar acceptor and sugar–sugar H-bonds are weakened by 0.5 kcal/mol,⁴⁷ and (iii) the latest optimized gHBfix version from 2021 (either gHBfix_{opt} or gHBfix21 subvariant).⁵⁶ In the gHBfix_{opt} version, all RNA H-bond donor...H-bond acceptor interactions are modified, i.e., base donor–base acceptor, base donor–sugar acceptor, base donor–phosphate acceptor, sugar donor–base acceptor, sugar donor–sugar acceptor, and sugar donor–phosphate acceptor are adjusted specifically (see ref 56 for full description). The gHBfix_{opt} version was obtained by

machine learning, but then the modification of sugar donor–sugar acceptor interactions was excluded because it caused spurious destabilization of A-minor type I interaction in simulations of RNA kink-turn motif. This led to the final gHBfix21 version.⁵⁶ Both gHBfix_{opt} and gHBfix21 versions are very similar (see Table S1 in Supporting Information for a complete list of interactions modified by gHBfix_{opt} and gHBfix21 potentials) and are expected to provide essentially identical performance for the folded UUCG TL which does not contain any sugar donor–sugar acceptor interactions.⁵⁶ Note that in this work some analyzed simulations were done with gHBfix_{opt} and some with gHBfix21 potentials but, for simplicity, only the gHBfix21 labeling is used henceforth (Table 1).

For the sake of completeness, we note that simulations with the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix_{UNCG19} *ff* also contained modified pairwise vdW parameters via breakage of combination (mixing) rules (the so-called nonbonded fix approach, NBfix)⁷⁰ for atoms involved in BPh interaction type 0 (OBPh).⁷¹ More specifically, we reduced the minimum-energy distance of Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential (i.e., the R_{ij} parameter) for the –H8...O5'– pair, i.e., between H5–OR atom types for purines (NBfix_{OBPh-pur}; Table 1).⁶³

The OL3 *ff* (the standard version without CP modification) was also tested with (i) adjusted vdW parameters (NBfix) of O2', terminal O3' and O5', and nonbridging phosphate (*pro-R_p*, *pro-S_p*) oxygens by Yang et al. (PAK *ff*)⁶² and with (ii) very recently suggested general adjustment of pairwise vdW parameters between oxygens and nonpolar hydrogens, i.e., the NBfix applied for most –CH...O– interactions involving nonpolar hydrogens (Hydrogen Repulsion Modification; HRM), using the R_{ij} value of 2.7 Å (OL3_{R2.7} *ff*;⁶¹ Table 1).

Other tested pair-additive *ffs* include (i) reparameterized charges, nonbonded and dihedral parameters by Tan and co-workers (DESRES *ff*),⁴⁴ (ii) subsequent further refinement of nonbonded parameters, charges, and dihedrals by the same group (DES-Amber *ff*),⁷² (iii) comprehensive reparameterization of all AMBER dihedral parameters by Aytenfisu et al. (ROC *ff*),⁴³ (iv) revised nonbonded and dihedral parameters by Chen and Garcia (Chen&Garcia *ff*),⁷³ (v) optimized nonbonded parameters with an inclusion of grid-based energy correction map (CMAP) term⁷⁴ by Li et al. (BSFF1 *ff*),⁷⁵ and the latest CHARMM⁷⁶ *ff* for RNA simulations (CHARMM36;⁷⁷ Table 1).

Both 14-mer and 8-mer UUCG TLs were placed in a cubic box of either OPC⁷⁸ (OL3, all OL3_{CP}-based variants, OL3_{R2.7}, ROC and PAK *ffs*), TIP4P-D⁷⁹ (DESRES *ff*), or TIP3P⁸⁰ (ROC and Chen&Garcia *ffs*) water molecules with minimal distance of 12 Å between the solute and the box border. KCl ions parametrized by Joung&Cheatham⁸¹ for the TIP4P-EW (OPC) or TIP3P water models were added to neutralize the system and to establish excess-salt ion concentration of ~0.15 M. We opted for the commonly used ~0.15 M KCl salt-excess in our standard MD simulations to mimic physiological ionic strength, ensuring realistic electrostatic screening and system stability under biologically relevant conditions. Simulations with DESRES *ff* were run with recommended^{44,82} charmm22 ions⁸³ and we further tested charmm22 ions in simulations with the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix19 *ff*. Simulations with Chen&Garcia and OL3_{R2.7} *ffs* were run with recommended Chen&Pappu⁸⁴ and Li&Merz⁸⁵ ions, respectively. The ROC *ff* was tested with both the OPC and TIP3P water models. Whereas simulations with the TIP3P water

model were performed under the excess salt concentration of ~ 0.1 M using NaCl ions (Joung&Cheatham parameters; as used in the original ROC paper⁴³), we also tested the performance of ROC *ff* with OPC water under the excess-salt concentration of ~ 0.15 M using KCl ions.

The tLeap program was used to generate initial files (with the exception of DES-Amber, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 *ffs*; see below) and simulations were subsequently performed in AMBER18⁸⁶ using the pmemd.MPI and pmemd.cuda⁸⁷ programs for equilibration and production simulations, respectively. All MD simulations were run at $T = 298$ K with the hydrogen mass repartitioning⁸⁸ allowing 4 fs integration time step. Long-range electrostatics were treated with particle mesh Ewald⁸⁹ and the distance cutoff for LJ interactions was set to 10 Å. The production simulations were performed in a constant volume ensemble and the temperature was regulated by a Langevin thermostat⁹⁰ (see Supporting Information of ref 18 for details about minimization and equilibration protocols). The production simulations were run for 20 μ s, and either 10 or 5 independent trajectories were obtained for each tested *ff*. In a few cases, we used trajectories from our previous papers (Table S2 in Supporting Information).

DES-Amber, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 simulations were performed in Gromacs2020.⁹¹ The DES-Amber parameters for Gromacs were obtained directly from the D. E. Shaw Research according to the procedure outlined in the original paper.⁷² The abbreviation DES-Amber in this paper thus refers to the Gromacs version of the DES-Amber 3.20 *ff*.⁷² We used the recommended TIP4P-D, TIP3P, and CHARMM-modified TIP3P (TIP3P_{CHARMM}) water models for DES-Amber, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 simulations, respectively. KCl ions described by charmm22, Joung&Cheatham, and CHARMM parameters for DES-Amber, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 simulations, respectively, were added to neutralize the system and to establish excess-salt ion concentration of 0.15 M. We note that the simulation protocol in Gromacs2020 slightly differed from the one in AMBER18 due to differences in simulation codes. Namely, Gromacs simulations were performed in a rhombic dodecahedral box and bonds involving hydrogens were constrained using the LINCS algorithm.⁹² The cutoff distance for the direct space summation of the electrostatic interactions was 10 Å and the simulations were performed at 298 K using the stochastic velocity rescaling thermostat⁹³ (see Table 1 for a summary of all tested *ffs*, water models, and ion parameters).

System Preparation and Simulation Protocols for Polarizable CHARMM_{Drude} and AMOEBA *ffs*. Ten pre-equilibrated structures of 14-mer UUCG TL prepared by the nonpolarizable OL3_{CP} *ff* were used as starting points for CHARMM_{Drude}^{94–97} and AMOEBA^{60,99} simulations. For the CHARMM_{Drude} *ff*, the structures were transformed into the polarizable model using the CHARMM software (version 44b1).⁷⁶ During the conversion process, Drude particles were introduced for all heavy atoms and lone pairs associated with each hydrogen acceptor. The OPC water molecules were converted into the polarizable SWM4-NDP model.⁹⁸ After initial minimization and equilibration procedure using the NAMD 2.13 package,¹⁰⁰ ten independent production simulations were performed at 298 K in OpenMM 8.0¹⁰¹ for the length of 5 μ s. Drude Langevin integrator^{102,103} was utilized with a time step of 1 fs. The pressure was maintained at 1 bar utilizing the Monte Carlo barostat.¹⁰⁴ The covalent bonds involving hydrogens were kept rigid using the SHAKE¹⁰⁵ and

SETTLE¹⁰⁶ algorithms for solute and water, respectively. A constraint of 0.2 Å was applied to limit the length of the Drude-nuclei bonds. Electrostatic interactions were treated using the particle-mesh Ewald method (PME)¹⁰⁷ with a 12 Å cutoff for the real space term. Nonbonded interactions were truncated at 12 Å using a switching function from 10 to 12 Å.

For the AMOEBA *ff*, pre-equilibrated UUCG TL structures were transferred into xyz files and minimized in 10,000 steps using the steepest descent method. The systems were then heated to 298 K and equilibrated at a pressure of 1 bar. Stochastic velocity rescale thermostat⁹³ and Monte Carlo barostat^{104,108} with coupling constants of 0.1 ps were used to maintain temperature and pressure, respectively. The applied real-space cutoffs for electrostatics and van der Waals were 7 and 12 Å, respectively. RESPA integrator¹⁰⁹ was used with the integration step of 1 and 2 fs for equilibration and production simulations, respectively. Other control functions and parameters were set to their default values. Ten independent simulations were run for 5 μ s in the NVT ensemble using the GPU-accelerated Tinker code¹¹⁰ (see Table 1 for a summary of all tested pair-additive and polarizable *ffs*).

Enhanced Sampling Folding Simulations. We used a combination of well-tempered metadynamics (MetaD)^{111–113} and replica exchange with solute tempering (REST2),¹¹⁴ i.e., the ST-MetaD method,⁶³ for folding simulations of the r(gcUUCGgc) 8-mer TL. ST-MetaD simulations were performed with 12 replicas starting from unfolded single strands and were simulated in the effective temperature range of 298–497 K. We performed typically three independent ST-MetaD simulations for the tested *ffs*. The average acceptance rate was $\sim 30\%$. The ϵ RMSD metric¹¹⁵ was used as a biased collective variable using the reference native TL structure. ST-MetaD simulations were carried out using a GPU-capable version of GROMACS2018⁹¹ in combination with PLUMED 2.5^{116,117} and run for 5 μ s per replica; see ref 63 for further details about the ST-MetaD protocol and Table S2 in Supporting Information for a full list of standard and enhanced sampling simulations.

Comparison with NMR Data and Folding Experiments. Besides the detailed analysis of the structural developments in the simulations of the 14-mer UUCG TL, the structural ensembles were also compared with the available primary NMR data.^{36,50} We analyzed four NMR observables, i.e., (i) backbone 3J scalar couplings, (ii) sugar 3J scalar couplings, (iii) nuclear Overhauser effect intensities (NOEs), and (iv) ambiguous NOEs (ambNOEs) resulting from a sum of overlapping peaks. 3J scalar couplings were calculated via Karplus relationships, NOEs were obtained as averages over the N samples, and ambNOEs were calculated by summing the contribution from either two, three, or four nuclei pairs and again averaged over the N samples (see ref 19 for details). A combination of all those analyzed NMR observables (calculated as weighted arithmetic mean) provided the total χ^2 value for each MD simulation. In principle, the lower the total χ^2 value, the better the agreement between the experiment and the predicted data from the MD simulation. However, as most of the considered NMR signals are either intranucleotide and/or from stem residues, local deviations of loop residue(s) from native conformation were typically not visibly reflected by the χ^2 analysis (see the paragraph “Interpretation of Measured NMR signals of the 14-mer UUCG TL is not straightforward” in Results and Discussions).

ST-MetaD simulations of the 8-mer UUCG TL provided populations of the native structure and other conformations, which can be used for estimation of the folding free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{fold}}^{\circ}$)⁶³ and directly compared with available experimental data.^{32–35} Reference native structure of the 8-mer UUCG TL was taken from our previous work.¹⁸ The ϵ RMSD threshold separating the folded and un(mis)folded states was set at a value of 0.7 (see ref 63 for details about $\Delta G_{\text{fold}}^{\circ}$ estimations and convergence).

Analysis and Definition of Important States. We identified a number of alternative (nonnative) substrates that are significantly populated during MD simulation with certain *ffs* instead of the native TL state; see the paragraph “Description of alternative (misfolded) states of the UUCG TL identified in MD simulations” in Results and Discussion. Those were identified by visual inspection of all trajectories via VMD¹¹⁸ and PyMOL¹¹⁹ and characterized in detail by CPPTRAJ.¹²⁰ Coordinates of characterized misfolded states are attached as PDB files in the [Supporting Information](#).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We performed an extended set of standard MD simulations of one of the most common RNA benchmark structures, the 2KOC NMR structure³⁶ of the 14-mer UUCG TL with five base pairs in the stem, using a variety of RNA *ffs* including polarizable ones. We then carried out a set of folding (biased) simulations for selected *ffs* (those best performing for the folded TL) using the 8-mer UUCG TL. Finally, we ran standard simulations of some other systems, to better understand properties of specific *ffs*. In total, we analyzed 130 standard MD simulations of the UUCG 14-mer with a cumulative time of 2300 μ s, 16 ST-MetaD simulations of the UUCG 8-mer with 12 replicas and cumulative time of 960 μ s, and additional 63 simulations of other systems with a cumulative time of 368 μ s, resulting in more than 3.6 ms of simulation data (Tables S2 and S3 in Supporting Information). We first introduce the native UUCG TL structure with its key interactions and define all alternative states that are sampled in the simulations. Next, we describe the most common disruption and (in a few cases) refolding pathways of the UUCG TL in simulations with different *ffs*. Then, we present UUCG 8-mer folding simulations for three *ffs* that are best performing in the standard simulations. Since we obtained striking differences in folding free energies among these *ffs*, we further inspected their performance using standard simulations for additional NA systems. Finally, we provide a brief synthesis of the data and our perspective on the current state of the art and future development of RNA *ffs*.

Native Structure of UUCG TL. The 2KOC NMR structure³⁶ contains five base-pair canonical stem (G_1C_{14} , G_2C_{13} , C_3G_{12} , A_4U_{11} and C_5G_{10} base pairs) and four U_6 , U_7 , C_8 and G_9 loop nucleotides (Figure 1). The UUCG TL native state contains a *trans*-wobble G_9U_6 base pair which requires G_9 to adopt an unusual *syn* conformation. The *trans*-wobble G_9U_6 base pair is stabilized by a $G_9(N1H)\cdots U_6(O2)$ H-bond and two $U_6(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(O6)$ and $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(N7)$ sugar–base H-bonds (Figure 1).^{36,57–59} The U_7 nucleotide is flipped out into the solution and thus expected to be mobile. C_8 is interacting with a U_6 phosphate moiety and forms a $C_8(N4H)\cdots U_6(\text{pro-R}_p)$ H-bond (the base–phosphate interaction type 7; 7BPh).⁷¹ The U_7 and C_8 nucleotides are also characterized by the unusual south-type ribose conformations ($C2'$ -endo pucker; Figure 1).^{36,57–59}

r(ggcacUUCGgugcc) 14-mer

Figure 1. Secondary and tertiary structure of the 14-mer UUCG TL. Secondary structure annotation (left panel) follows the Leontis–Westhof nomenclature¹²¹ and residue labeling is consistent with the experimental structure (PDB ID 2KOC³⁶). Both 7BPh interaction⁷¹ and key G_9 nucleotide with *syn* conformation of χ_{G9} dihedral are highlighted. Panel on the right shows the starting snapshot for MD simulations. A, C, G and U nucleotides are colored sand, white, red, and blue, respectively. H-atoms, ions, and water molecules are not shown for clarity. Key structural features of UUCG TL are colored in green and include *syn*-conformation of χ_{G9} dihedral and $C2'$ -endo pucker of U_7 and C_8 riboses. Green dashed lines show the native H-bonds with involved heavy atoms explicitly labeled, i.e., $G_9(N1H)\cdots U_6(O2)$, $U_6(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(O6)$, $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(N7)$, and $C_8(N4H)\cdots U_6(\text{pro-R}_p)$. Thin green dashed lines indicate two non-native H-bonds, i.e., $G_9(N2H)\cdots U_6(O2)$ and $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(O6)$ that are frequently established during MD simulations.

In previous simulation studies, we observed two alternative $G_9(N2H)\cdots U_6(O2)$ and $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(O6)$ H-bonds, which were often established when the native $G_9(N1H)\cdots U_6(O2)$ and $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(N7)$ H-bonds were weakened or broken (Figure 1). Those alternative H-bonds appear to assist in the stabilization of the highly mobile G_9 in the binding pocket and to maintain its *syn* conformation.⁴⁷

Here, we used the following criteria to determine that the UUCG TL is sampling the native state: all four native $G_9(N1H)\cdots U_6(O2)$, $U_6(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(O6)$, $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(N7)$ and $C_8(N4H)\cdots U_6(\text{pro-R}_p)$ H-bonds are established with distance between proton donor and proton acceptor ≤ 3.5 Å; slightly higher cutoff of 3.7 Å was used for the $C_8(N4H)\cdots U_6(\text{pro-R}_p)$ H-bond. Furthermore, G_9 is sampling the *syn* conformation defined by χ_{G9} dihedral $G_9(O4')-G_9(C1')-G_9(N9)-G_9(C4)$ between -25 and 115° ; Table 2.

Description of Alternative (Misfolded) States of the UUCG TL Identified in MD Simulations. Structural dynamics of the UUCG TL sampled by the tested RNA *ffs* were characterized by a variety of alternative (misfolded) loop conformations. We carefully inspected all MD trajectories and grouped these alternative conformations into ten different states (Table 2 and Figure 2). They were sampled during both disruption and refolding back to the native state of the UUCG

Table 2. Summarized Labeling and Structural Criteria Used for Characterization of Alternative (Misfolded) States Occurring during MD Simulations of the 14-mer UUCG TL

state	RMSD from start ^a	clustering criteria	Figure 2 label
<i>native</i>	0.9 ± 0.8	G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) distance <3.5 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance <3.5 Å, U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distance <3.5 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance <3.7 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	A
<i>sugar-base (N7) lost</i>	1.0 ± 0.8	at least one of G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) and G ₉ (N2)-U ₆ (O2) distances <3.5 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance <3.5 Å, U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distance >3.5 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance <3.7 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	B
<i>7BPh lost</i>	1.0 ± 0.8	at least one of G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) and G ₉ (N2)-U ₆ (O2) distances <3.5 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance <3.5 Å, U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distance <4.0 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance >3.7 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	C
<i>Both sugar-base (N7, O6) lost</i>	1.1 ± 0.8	at least one of G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) and G ₉ (N2)-U ₆ (O2) distances <3.5 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance <3.5 Å, U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distance >3.5 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance <3.7 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	D
<i>C₈ bulge + one sugar-base lost</i>	3.0 ± 0.8	at least one of G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) and G ₉ (N2)-U ₆ (O2) distances <3.5 Å, at least one of U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) and U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distances >3.5 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance >5.0 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	E
<i>G₉ bulge (syn)</i>	2.4 ± 0.6	G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) distance >5.0 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance >5.0 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>, RMSD of loop nucleotides <3.0 Å	F
<i>G₉ bulge (anti, high-anti)</i>	2.6 ± 0.7	G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) distance >5.0 Å, U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance >5.0 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral either <-180°, -25°> or <115°, 180°>, RMSD of loop nucleotides <3.0 Å	G
<i>G₉ back in pocket (anti, high-anti)</i>	1.8 ± 0.7	G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) distance <5.2 Å, at least one of the following two criteria was true: U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) distance <3.7 Å and C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance <4.2 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral either <-180°, -25°> or <115°, 180°>, RMSD of loop nucleotides <3.0 Å	H
<i>U₆ + U₇ + C₈ bulge</i>	3.5 ± 1.0	G ₉ (N1)-U ₆ (O2) distance >5.0 Å, at least one of U ₆ (O2')-G ₉ (O6) and U ₇ (O2')-G ₉ (N7) distances <4.0 Å, C ₈ (N4)-U ₆ (<i>pro-R_p</i>) distance >5.0 Å, G ₉ (O4')-G ₉ (C1')-G ₉ (N9)-G ₉ (C4) dihedral <-25°,115°>	I
<i>loop disrupted</i>	4.2 ± 1.2	RMSD of loop nucleotides >3.0 Å, except when being included in the U ₆ + U ₇ + C ₈ bulge state	J
<i>stem + loop disrupted</i>	4.3 ± 1.5	RMSD of all nucleotides >4.6 Å	K

^aAverages (with errors as standard deviations) from all structures belonging to the particular cluster from all simulations (considering all tested RNA *ffs*) are shown. RMSD was calculated for all heavy atoms of loop nucleotides, i.e., U₆, U₇, C₈ and G₉. The equilibrated experimental structure (i.e., the starting MD snapshot) was used as the reference.

TL. The states are ordered from those closest to the *native* state toward more disrupted structures.

The first three states, labeled as *sugar-base (N7) lost*, *7BPh lost* and *both sugar-base (N7, O6) lost* were structurally close to the *native* state and their common feature was that the G₉ remained in the binding pocket and maintained the *syn* conformation (Table 2 and Figure 2). Sampling of those states was usually reversible and most likely reflected the genuine dynamics within the loop due to thermal fluctuations. These states also occurred as (final) intermediates upon successful refolding from disrupted structures back to the *native* state. A common feature of these states was the partial shift of the G₉ within the binding pocket, characterized by formation of the alternative G₉(N2H)⋯U₆(O2) H-bond.⁴⁷ The *sugar-base (N7) lost* state contained structures with the G₉ in *syn* conformation, the *trans-wobble* G₉U₆ base pair formed (at least one of the native G₉(N1H)⋯U₆(O2) and alternative G₉(N2H)⋯U₆(O2) H-bonds was established) and the 7BPh interaction established by stable C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro-R_p*) H-bond. Further, the native U₆(2'-OH)⋯G₉(O6) sugar-base H-bond was formed but the other U₇(2'-OH)⋯G₉(N7) sugar-base H-bond was lost (the distance between U₇(O2') and G₉(N7) being greater than 3.5 Å). The *7BPh lost* state also contained structures with G₉ in *syn* and the *trans-wobble* G₉U₆ base pair formed. For this state, both native U₆(2'-OH)⋯G₉(O6) and U₇(2'-OH)⋯G₉(N7) sugar-base H-bonds were formed while the 7BPh interaction was lost (i.e., the distance between C₈(N4) and U₆(*pro-R_p*) exceeded 3.7 Å). Finally, the *both sugar-base (N7, O6) lost* state was also characterized by G₉ in *syn* and *trans-wobble* G₉U₆ base pair formed. The 7BPh interaction was established, but now both native sugar-base H-bonds were lost; i.e., the distances between the U₆(O2') and U₇(O2') hydroxyl oxygens and G₉(O6, N7) acceptors were greater than 3.5 Å; Table 2.

The next four states, termed as *C₈ bulge + one sugar-base lost*, *G₉ bulge (syn)*, *G₉ bulge (anti, high-anti)*, and *G₉ back in pocket (anti, high-anti)* could be categorized as partial

disruption of the loop (Table 2 and Figure 2). They involved a broader variety of conformations within each cluster, with details often dependent on the particular *ff*. Generally, these states assembled structures with either C₈ or G₉ flipped out and other misfolded structures with G₉ back in the binding pocket with the nonnative *anti*/*high-anti* value of χ_{G9} dihedral. Occurrence of these states during MD simulation could be followed by further structural deformations with complete loss of the native UUCG TL fold. The *C₈ bulge + one sugar-base lost* state still included structures with G₉ in *syn* and *trans-wobble* G₉U₆ base pair formed. However, the 7BPh interaction was lost, C₈ more displaced (i.e., the distance between C₈(N4) and U₆(*pro-R_p*) was greater than 5.0 Å), and one of the native sugar-base H-bonds was lost, i.e., at least one of the distances between U₆(O2') and G₉(O6) and between U₇(O2') and G₉(N7) was greater than 3.5 Å. The *G₉ bulge (syn)* state was composed of structures with G₉ in *syn* conformation but repelled from the binding pocket, i.e., both distances between G₉(N1) and U₆(O2) and between U₆(O2') and G₉(O6) were greater than 5.0 Å while RMSD of loop nucleotides (involving all heavy atoms from U₆, U₇, C₈ and G₉ nucleotides) was less than 3.0 Å. Comparably, the *G₉ bulge (anti, high-anti)* state also involved structures with G₉ repelled from the binding pocket (with similar criteria as for the *G₉ bulge (syn)* state) but G₉ was sampling either *anti* or *high-anti* values of χ_{G9} dihedral. Both the *G₉ bulge (syn)* and *G₉ bulge (anti, high-anti)* states included structures independently of the state of the 7BPh interaction (i.e., both states contained structures where the 7BPh interaction could be both established and weakened/disrupted). The *G₉ back in pocket (anti, high-anti)* state encompassed a variety of structures, where G₉ entered back into the binding pocket but in *anti*/*high-anti* orientation of χ_{G9} dihedral, the distance between G₉(N1) and U₆(O2) was less than 5.2 Å, at least one of the distances between U₆(O2') and G₉(O6) and between C₈(N4) and U₆(*pro-R_p*) was less than 3.7 and 4.2 Å, respectively, and the RMSD of loop nucleotides

Figure 2. Representative snapshots of all important structural states frequently occurring during MD simulations of the 14-mer UUCG TL. See the legend to Figure 1 for nucleotide color scheme. Occurrence of key structural features that were monitored for characterization of each state, i.e., *syn* conformation of G₉ nucleotide, G₉(N1H)⋯U₆(O2), G₉(N2H)⋯U₆(O2), U₆(2′-OH)⋯G₉(O6), U₇(2′-OH)⋯G₉(N7), and C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro-R_p*) H-bonds, is explicitly highlighted by green lines within each structure; see Table 2 for detailed description. Color labeling of the names of all states will be used later in the paper.

was less than 3.0 Å. G₉ could reform the base pair with U₆ but in a variety of nonnative orientations, including the formation of nonnative *trans* Watson–Crick/Hoogsteen¹²¹ GU base pair with the formation of U₆(N3H)⋯G₉(O6/N7) H-bond. The majority of structures belonging to this state had at least one of the 7BPh and U₆(2′-OH)⋯G₉(O6) H-bonds established.

The remaining three characterized states, termed U₆ + U₇ + C₈ *bulge*, *loop disrupted*, and *stem+loop disrupted*, implicated more severe disruptions of the loop (Table 2 and Figure 2). The U₆ + U₇ + C₈ *bulge* state involved a broad variety of

structures where G₉ maintained the *syn* conformation and remained in the binding pocket but the *trans*-wobble G₉U₆ base pair was completely disrupted (the distance between G₉(N1) and U₆(O2) was greater than 5.0 Å). The 7BPh interaction was lost as the C₈ was dislocated (the distance between C₈(N4) and U₆(*pro-R_p*) was greater than 5.0 Å) and at least one of the distances between U₆(O2′) and G₉(O6) and between U₇(O2′) and G₉(N7) was less than 4.0 Å. In summary, this state involved quite disrupted loop structures with the G₉ maintaining its native conformation, often

Figure 3. continued

Figure 3. Structural dynamics of the 14-mer UUCG TL obtained by various RNA *ffs* in 20 μ s-long standard MD simulations. Each panel is labeled by the applied *ff*, water model and ion parameters (see Table 1). Panels show evolution of characterized states highlighted by different colors; see Figure 2 for representative snapshots and Table 2 for a detailed description. Comparison with the NMR data is shown next to each tested RNA *ff* as total χ^2 values, see Methods. They were calculated for each simulation (values on the right) and as averages (over ten simulations as standard deviations).

stabilized by one native sugar–base interaction. The *loop disrupted* state was defined just by RMSD of loop nucleotides greater than 3.0 Å, except for structures that were already characterized, i.e., there was a partial overlap between this state and the previous one as some structures belonging to the $U_6 + U_7 + C_8$ bulge state could also have RMSD of loop nucleotides greater than 3.0 Å. Some structures belonging to the *loop-disrupted* state could have one native interaction established (typically the 7BPh interaction) as only the RMSD value was used for the definition of structures belonging to this state. Finally, the *stem + loop disrupted* state involved structures with RMSD of all residues greater than 4.6 Å (including all heavy atoms from the 14 nucleotides). This criterion overrides all other state definitions and includes structures not only with full displacement of loop nucleotides but usually also those where the canonical loop-closing C_5G_{10} base pair (or even more stem base pairs) was disrupted.

OL3_{CP} with gHBfix Potentials, DESRES, DES-Amber, OL3_{R2.7}, and PAK *ffs* Revealed Fully or Reasonably Stable UUCG TL Dynamics. Figure 3 summarizes the initial set of RNA *ffs* that demonstrated improved performance for the structural description of the 14-mer UUCG TL.

Initially, we investigated the behavior of gHBfix21,⁵⁶ gHBfix_{UNCG19},⁴⁷ and gHBfix19¹⁸ potentials applied in combination with the OL3_{CP}^{28–31,68,69} RNA *ff* variant. OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 simulations revealed entirely stable dynamics of the UUCG TL.⁵⁶ The *native* state was lost in two out of ten OL3_{CP}–gHBfix_{UNCG19} simulations and in all ten OL3_{CP}–gHBfix19 simulations on the 20 μ s-long time scale (Figure 3). We also tested charmm22 ion parameters (see ref 82 for the

explanation) in OL3_{CP}–gHBfix19 simulations (see Methods and Table 1). The overall sampling of the *native* state was still rather unsatisfactory, although with one refolding event and one stable trajectory (Figure 3). A common feature of OL3_{CP}–gHBfix simulations was that sampling of the *native* state was accompanied by short reversible occurrences of the *sugar-base (N7) lost* and *7BPh lost* states, i.e., reversible weakening of the native $U_7(2'-OH)\cdots G_9(N7)$ and $C_8(N4H)\cdots U_6(\text{pro-R}_p)$ H-bonds. Reversible distortions of the loop occurred via flips of either C_8 (from the *7BPh lost* state to the C_8 bulge + one sugar-base lost state) or G_9 (from the G_9 bulge (*syn*) state to the G_9 bulge (*anti, high-anti*) state); refolding back to the *native* state was possible (Figure 3). Note that the occurrence of the C_8 bulge + one sugar-base lost state at the very end of sim #7 with the gHBfix21 was reversible and we actually observed refolding back to the *native* state at $\sim 20.4 \mu$ s upon prolongation of the simulation.⁵⁶

Simulations with DESRES *ff* provided quite a good description of the UUCG TL (Figure 3).⁸² Comparably to OL3_{CP}–gHBfix19 simulations, loss of the *native* state occurred via flip of either C_8 or G_9 out of its binding conformation, i.e., via C_8 bulge + one sugar-base lost, G_9 bulge (*syn*) or G_9 bulge (*anti, high-anti*) states. Refolding back to the *native* state was also possible and four out of 10 simulations maintained the *native* state after 20 μ s (Figure 3). DES-Amber *ff* achieved fully stable dynamics of the 14-mer UUCG TL, where (similarly to the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 simulations) sampling of the dominant *native* state was alternating with very short visits of the *sugar-base (N7) lost* and *7BPh lost* states (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Structural dynamics of the 14-mer UUCG TL obtained by another set of pair-additive RNA *ffs*. Each panel shows evolution of the characterized states in five 20 μ s-long standard MD simulations. See the legend of Figure 3 for more details.

A fully stable structural description of the UUCG TL was also achieved with the OL3_{R2.7} *ff*. We evidenced one flip of G₉ out of the binding pocket in sim #7, followed by a sampling of G₉ bulge (*anti, high-anti*), G₉ back in the pocket (*anti, high-anti*), and loop disrupted states. This lasted for $\sim 8 \mu$ s, but then the *syn* conformation of χ_{G_9} dihedral was restored, G₉ returned to the binding pocket, and the *native* state was neatly re-established (Figure 3). Interestingly, the 7BPh lost state, i.e., the reversible weakening of the native C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro-R_p*) H-bond (Figure 2) occurred significantly less frequently than in simulations with OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21 and DES-Amber *ffs* (both the latter having comparable performance; Figure 3). Hence, the 7BPh interaction in the UUCG TL is probably indirectly stabilized by the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* due to the reduction of -CH⋯O-steric conflicts in the loop.⁶¹

Finally, simulations with PAK *ff* revealed a reasonable structural description of the UUCG TL. The overall sampling of structural states was comparable with OL3_{CP}-gHBfix19 and

DESRES *ffs*. Three out of 10 simulations maintained the native state after 20 μ s (Figure 3) which included two successful refoldings back to the *native* state from more disrupted states, i.e., those where G₉ left the binding site.

In summary, OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21, DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} *ffs* provide entirely stable structural description of the UUCG TL during our standard 10 \times 20 μ s simulations.

Other Pair-Additive RNA *ffs* Provided Unstable Description of the UUCG TL. Figure 4 summarizes data for the standard OL3 *ff* and compares them with other pair-additive RNA *ffs*, namely, Chen&Garcia, ROC, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 *ffs*.

It has been known for almost a decade that the standard AMBER⁶⁷ OL3 RNA *ff*²⁸⁻³¹ (including its versions with modified phosphate oxygens⁶⁸)^{40,69} struggles with the structural description of the UUCG TL; note that the OL3 *ff* has been used in the past also under different names, such as bsc0 χ_{OL3} , χ_{OL3} , or ff10, ff12 and ff14 AMBER RNA *ff*.

Independent studies reported instability of the UUCG native structure in various standard as well as enhanced sampling simulations.^{9,15,41,43,46,47,61,74} For the sake of completeness of our comparison, we performed the 2KOC OL3 test (five trajectories) as for the other *ffs*. With the OPC water model, the OL3 *ff* gives the lifetime of the *native* UUCG structure close to 10 μ s, with one trajectory stable until the end (Figure 4). We did not detect any successful refolding back to the *native* state from more disrupted states, i.e., those where G₉ left the binding site.

Simulations with Chen&Garcia *ff* provided strikingly different outcomes in comparison with all other pair-additive *ffs*. The overall population of the *native* state was rather low (in agreement with the previous study using the shorter 10-mer UUCG TL).¹⁵ The *native* state could be re-established rather easily from a variety of more disrupted structures but was then again swiftly lost. We observed major dynamics of the loop characterized by sampling all of the classified misfolded states and additional ones belonging to the *loop disrupted* state. In other words, UUCG TL simulated by the Chen&Garcia *ff* was characterized by sustained dynamics of loop nucleotides coupled with stable base pairing within the stem. Perturbation of the *native* state was typically initiated via loss of the native C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro*-R_p) H-bond (7*BPh lost* state) followed by the flip of C₈ out of its binding position (C₈ *bulge + one sugar-base lost* state) and then typically reached states with complete repositioning of other loop nucleotides.

The ROC *ff* did not provide a good structural description of the UUCG TL, regardless of its combination with either TIP3P (as originally suggested)⁴³ or OPC water (Table 1). In agreement with the original work,⁴³ we observed abrupt and irreversible loss of the *native* state within the first few hundreds of ns. Disruptions started with the loss of native C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro*-R_p) H-bond (7*BPh lost* state) and were followed by repositioning of either one, two, or all three pyrimidine loop nucleotides (U₆, U₇, and C₈). Hence, the UUCG TL with ROC *ff* was characterized by frequent sampling of C₈ *bulge + one sugar-base lost* and U₆ + U₇ + C₈ *bulge* states (Figure 4) where native H-bonds were lost (Figure 2). Although we also detected states with G₉ flipped out to solvent, G₉ typically maintained its *syn* conformation of the χ_{G9} dihedral state and remained within the binding pocket despite the loss of all native H-bonds (the U₆ + U₇ + C₈ *bulge* state).

With BSFF1 *ff* the *native* state was lost in all five simulations within the first few hundreds of ns. This was followed by a complete rearrangement of loop nucleotides with a weakening of stem base pairs during the later stages of the simulations (Figure 4). Loop disruption was initiated by reversible flips of G₉ out of the binding pocket (the G₉ *bulge (syn)* state). Once G₉ lost its *syn* conformation (the G₉ *bulge (anti, high-anti)* state), additional irreversible repositioning of the remaining loop nucleotides occurred. Then the disruption propagated toward the stem where the closing C₅G₁₀ base pair was broken (i.e., the *stem-loop disrupted* state was sampled; Figures 2 and 4).

Significant UUCG TL deformations occurred with CHARMM36 *ff*. We observed abrupt loss of all native interactions and flip of G₉ out of the binding pocket within the first few ns of simulations, just after the initial equilibrations (Figure 4). The relocation of G₉ was immediately followed by a loss of remaining native interactions and resulted in complete distortion of the native arrangement. We also detected frequent loss of canonical base pairing in the

stem with the possible occurrence of completely unfolded structures in later stages of the simulations.

In summary, our extensive testing revealed that the structural description of the UUCG *native* state is a significant challenge for several RNA *ffs*. Apart from the standard OL3 *ff*, all remaining *ffs* summarized in Figure 4 were characterized by a swift loss of the UUCG native arrangement and sampling of alternative states. We observed that only Chen&Garcia *ff* was able to intermittently reestablish the *native* state from alternative misfolded states though only for very short times (typically tens up to hundreds of ns). OL3, ROC, BSFF1, and CHARMM36 *ffs* were characterized by irreversible loss of the native arrangement. BSFF1 and CHARMM36 *ffs* even sampled structures with broken canonical base pairs within the stem during later stages of MD simulations.

Polarizable *ffs* Also Face Challenges in Accurate Description of the UUCG TL Structure. We included two available polarizable RNA *ffs* in our set of simulations. Although both CHARMM_{Drude} and AMOEBA *ffs* are used with GPU-accelerated versions of particular MD engines, i.e., OpenMM and Tinker-HP, we still obtained at least an order of magnitude slower performance (using Nvidia RTX 3080 Ti GPU cards) in comparison with pair-additive *ffs* utilized by either pmemd.cuda⁸⁷ in AMBER or GPU accelerated GROMACS code. Thus, the presented results by polarizable *ffs* are based on shorter 5 μ s-long MD simulations.

Both CHARMM_{Drude} and AMOEBA *ffs* revealed comparable behavior in structural description of the UUCG TL characterized initially by reversible loss of the *native* state and frequent sampling of alternative 7*BPh lost*, C₈ *bulge + one sugar-base lost* and U₆ + U₇ + C₈ *bulge* states (Figure 5), i.e., those states where G₉ remained in the binding pocket in its native *syn* conformation of the χ_{G9} dihedral (Figure 2). In other words, reversible loss of the *native* state started with breakage of the native C₈(N4H)⋯U₆(*pro*-R_p) H-bond (7*BPh lost* state). It was followed by disruption of native sugar–base interaction and further repositioning of either one, two, or all three pyrimidine loop nucleotides (U₆, U₇, and C₈). However, we did not see any successful refolding back to the *native* state (on the limited 5 μ s-long time scale) by both polarizable *ffs* once G₉ left the pocket and lost its *syn* conformation, which occurred in four and five simulations (out of ten) with CHARMM_{Drude} and AMOEBA *ffs*, respectively (Figure 5).

Specific development was seen in sim #9 and sims #2 and #3 with CHARMM_{Drude} and AMOEBA *ffs*, respectively. We observed abrupt loop disruption during CHARMM_{Drude} sim #9 characterized by repositioning of all three U₆, U₇, and C₈ pyrimidine loop nucleotides (from 7*BPh lost*, via C₈ *bulge + one sugar-base lost* toward *loop disrupted* state). However, G₉ remained in position sampling its native *syn* conformation but U₆ left the binding pocket and all H-bonds with G₉ were broken. This unusual state falls rather “accidentally” within the clustering criteria of the G₉ *bulge (syn)* state (see dark-blue hit on Figure 5 and state definition in Table 2). As the G₉ remained in the pocket in its *syn* state, refolding back to the *native* state was possible, and in fact, we detected successful refolding and complete reestablishment of all native interactions after ~600 ns of MD sim #9. Nevertheless, 7*BPh lost* and C₈ *bulge + one sugar-base lost* states were dominantly sampled during the later stages of this simulation (Figure 5).

Other unusual states were frequently sampled near the end of sims #2 and #3 using AMOEBA *ff*. These states are marked

Figure 5. Structural dynamics of the 14-mer UUCG TL obtained by polarizable RNA *ffs*. Each panel shows evolution of characterized states in ten 5 μ s-long simulations. See the legend in Figure 3 for more details.

as G_9 back in pocket (*anti, high-anti*) state (see cyan marks in Figure 5 and clustering criteria in Table 2) and, indeed, are characterized by repositioning of G_9 back to the binding pocket with noncanonical *anti/high-anti* conformation of the χ_{G_9} dihedral. Intriguingly, all native H-bond interactions were reestablished with G_9 in a *high-anti* state, which required visibly deeper insertion of G_9 into the binding pocket, noncanonical C2'-endo sugar pucker of G_9 , and other major deformations along the sugar–phosphate backbone (see Figure S1 in the Supporting Information for a direct comparison of the *native* state and this unusual “native-like” state).

In summary, both tested polarizable RNA *ffs* struggled with the description of the UUCG *native* state. We observed frequent refolding back to the *native* state from partially disrupted structures, but we did not detect any successful restoration of the native arrangement once G_9 left the binding pocket and lost its canonical *syn* conformation. The *native* state was not dominantly populated as alternative loop arrangements were favored by both polarizable *ffs*.

Interpretation of Measured NMR Signals of the 14-mer UUCG TL Is Not Straightforward. Besides the detailed structure monitoring and clustering given above, we also analyzed available 63 backbone 3J-couplings, 33 sugar 3J-couplings, 253 NOEs, and 27 ambNOEs signals used to refine the NMR structure.^{36,50} For each signal, we calculated differences between predicted (MD data) and experimentally observed values, and all of them were subsequently combined

(see Methods), which resulted in a total χ^2 value for each MD simulation (Figures 3–5). Calculated χ^2 values from all simulations by different RNA *ffs* were distributed between 0.90 and 2.57, where values around and below 1.0 usually indicate good agreement with the experiment (considering experimental errors). In general, *ffs* providing reasonably stable UUCG TL dynamics revealed χ^2 values typically from ~ 1.0 to ~ 1.2 whereas those struggling to sample the *native* state provided higher χ^2 values $> \sim 1.5$. However, this was true for cases in which larger structural distortions often affecting canonical base pairing in the stem were detected. On the other hand, we found out that extensive sampling of structures rather close to the *native* state (i.e., *sugar-base (N7) lost, 7BPh lost* and *both sugar-base (N7, O6) lost* states) and even those considered as more disrupted states (including the *loop disrupted* state with RMSD of loop nucleotides greater than 3.0 Å; see Table 2) could also provide low total χ^2 values. In fact, we evidenced several examples where irreversible loss of the *native* state and substantial sampling of states with disrupted native loop arrangement provided lower total χ^2 values than simulations where the *native* state was the dominant sampled structure (Figures 3–5). Furthermore, we observed cases where two simulations (even with the same *ff*) sampled comparable structural states (including the *native* state, close to native and more disrupted states) and revealed quite different total χ^2 values (Figures 3–5).

In summary, available NMR structural data for the UUCG TL must be used carefully for assessing the performance of *ffs* during MD simulations. Disagreement between predicted and measured NMR signals revealed bigger structural problems in a simulation but did not correlate well with local dynamics within the loop, i.e., with (ir)reversible loss of the *native* state and sampling of alternative loop conformations. We identified that repositioning of one (or even two) loop nucleotide (i.e., minor loop distortion) resulted in just a few violated NMR signals. Those discrepancies usually vanished upon averaging the data using the entire set of 376 signals during the calculation of the total χ^2 value. Although our MD simulations were conducted under ionic conditions slightly different from those of the NMR experiment (0.02 M potassium phosphate), this difference is not expected to affect the comparison. In addition, the UUCG TL belongs to prominent autonomous RNA motifs, which are known to fold into their native structures rather independently of their context and surrounding environment.¹²²

Hence, our results confirm that the structural interpretation of NMR data for dynamic RNA molecules (even for small systems like the 14-mer UUCG TL) is rather complex.⁵⁰ To precisely evaluate loop behavior during MD simulations of UUCG TL using NMR data, it is necessary to focus on specific NMR signals from loop nucleotides rather than relying solely on a comparison between predicted and measured signals across all available data (the total χ^2 value).

Folding Simulations of the 8-mer UUCG TL Revealed That the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 *ff* Currently Provides the Most Accurate Folding Free Energy Estimate. The OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21, DES-Amber, and OL3_{R2.7} RNA *ffs* achieved fully satisfactory performance for the structural description of the 14-mer UUCG TL in standard simulations. Thus, we used the 8-mer UUCG TL to test these three *ffs* using ST-MetaD folding simulations initiated from the single-strand A-form conformation (see Methods). The 8-mer having an A-RNA stem with only two base pairs is an ideal target for such

comparison as its structures in solution are in a dynamic temperature-dependent equilibrium between folded and unfolded states.^{32–35} The *ffs* should describe well not only the *native* state but also its balance with the misfolded/unfolded ensemble.⁶³ We performed three independent ST-MetaD simulations for all three tested *ffs* and obtained a staggering difference between the calculated $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energies. Averages over the three simulations predicted $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ values of 0.0 ± 0.6 kcal/mol with OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21, 2.4 ± 0.8 kcal/mol with DES-Amber, and 7.4 ± 0.2 kcal/mol with OL3_{R2.7}. Thus, the $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energy obtained with the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 combination predicted the highest population of the native state at 298 K (Table 3) and the calculated $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energy is quite close to the available experimental data (reported values are between -1.6 and -0.7 kcal/mol).^{32–35} The present OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 result is comparable with a single simulation reported earlier ($\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ of 0.5 ± 0.1 kcal/mol).⁵⁶ For overall

comparison, we also calculated $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energies (single ST-MetaD runs) with three other *ffs* that provided a rather reasonable description of the 14-mer UUCG TL. For the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix_{UNCG19} *ff*, we obtained $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ of 1.9 ± 0.1 kcal/mol,⁶³ for the DESRES *ff* 5.1 ± 0.1 kcal/mol, and for PAK *ff* 6.7 ± 0.1 kcal/mol (Table 3).

Taking all the data together, we observed strikingly different performances of the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* in standard simulations of the 14-mer and folding simulations of the 8-mer UUCG TL (Figure 3 and Table 3). To further inspect this point, we performed ST-MetaD simulations with the standard (unmodified) OL3 *ff* using identical water, ion, and other setups as used with the OL3_{R2.7} *ff*. With OL3 we obtained an $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ of 6.7 ± 0.2 kcal/mol (average over three simulations, Table 3). Comparison of calculated $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energies obtained from OL3_{R2.7} and control OL3 simulations indicates that the NBfix modification of the $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions (the Hydrogen Repulsion Modification; HRM)⁶¹ does not bring any thermodynamic stabilization of the *native* state and could even have slightly opposite effect. To validate the convergence of estimated $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energies we monitored the number of folding events in continuous (demultiplexed) replicas from all ST-MetaD simulations and evidenced comparable behavior of all tested *ffs* (Figures S2–S17 in Supporting Information). We also inspected folding pathways in demultiplexed replicas and found out that all tested *ffs* lead to an essentially identical folding mechanism with two dominant pathways. Either the base pair stem forms first, followed by the completion of the loop, or the loop folds first, and then the stem follows. This could be partially affected by the chosen collective variable (ϵRMSD) but it may also reflect the genuine simplicity of the 8-mer system. The observed folding landscape is schematically depicted in Figure S18 in Supporting Information. Hence, we suggest that the unexpectedly high $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ energies obtained with the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* are not caused by the lack of folding events, but rather reflect an imbalance between folded (*native*) and misfolded/unfolded ensembles, i.e., the *native* state is energetically disfavored in comparison with other states.

In summary, despite comparable results in standard simulations of the 14-mer UUCG TL (Figure 3), we obtained strikingly different outcomes for the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21, DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} RNA *ffs* in folding simulations of the 8-mer UUCG TL. The OL3_{CP}–gHBfix21 combination provided a population of the *native* state rather consistent with experimental data. Obviously, this result should not be overinterpreted as the folding energy of the UUCG TL was directly included in the training data set of this *ff*. The DES-Amber *ff* underestimates the thermodynamic stability of the UUCG TL, however, in line with the standard simulations, it shows a clear improvement over the DESRES *ff*. In the DES-Amber paper, the authors stated that RNA hairpins are thermodynamically under-stabilized by 3–5 kcal/mol (see Supporting Information of ref 72) which is consistent with the data reported here. The discrepancy could be caused, for example, by the underestimated stability of the A-RNA stem or by some other reasons.^{14–16,18,41} Interestingly, while the original DESRES *ff* paper suggests that the thermodynamic stability of A-RNA duplexes is overestimated,⁴⁴ the DES-Amber *ff* paper suggests that this *ff* should give rather correct thermodynamics for the A-RNA duplexes.⁷² The OL3_{R2.7} data is entirely counterintuitive (Table 3). While OL3_{R2.7} dramatically improves the *kinetic* stability of the folded UUCG TL compared to standard OL3 *ff*, it, at the same

Table 3. Calculated Folding Free Energies ($\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$) and Expected Populations of the Native State at 298 K ($P_{\text{native, 298 K}}$) for the 8-mer UUCG TL^a

RNA <i>ff</i>	$\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ (kcal/mol)	$P_{\text{native, 298 K}}$ (%)
OL3 _{CP} –gHBfix21	-0.2 ± 0.6	58.6 ± 23.0
	0.2 ± 0.1	42.2 ± 3.8
	0.0 ± 0.2	49.7 ± 6.1
DES-Amber	2.2 ± 0.8	2.6 ± 0.4
	2.6 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.2
	2.3 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.4
OL3 _{R2.7}	7.6 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
	7.5 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
	7.0 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
OL3 _{CP} –gHBfix21 ^b	0.5 ± 0.1	31.2 ± 3.0
OL3 _{CP} –gHBfix _{UNCG19} ^c	1.9 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.8
DESRES	5.1 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
PAK	6.7 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
OL3 ^d	7.0 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
	7.0 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
	6.2 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0
Exp. ^e	$<-1.6, -0.7>$	$<75, 94>$

^aFolding free energies ($\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$) were calculated from populations of the *native* state and other states obtained from 5 μs -long ST-MetaD simulations with 12 replicas (see Methods). Statistical errors were calculated by estimating higher and lower boundaries of populations of the *native* state which were obtained from concatenated trajectories and bootstrapping with 16 blocks (see ref 63 for details). ^bSimulation run with the original gHBfix_{opt} potential obtained directly by machine learning (see Methods for an explanation of the terminology); data taken from ref 56. ^cSimulation run with the NBfix_{OBPh} correction¹⁹ added to the OL3_{CP}–gHBfix_{UNCG19} *ff*. NBfix_{OBPh} modifies vdW parameters for $-\text{H8}\cdots\text{O5}'-$ and $-\text{H6}\cdots\text{O5}'-$ atom pairs for purines and pyrimidines, respectively; data taken from ref 63. ^dControl simulations with standard (unmodified) OL3 *ff* run with OPC water and Li&Merz ions, i.e., with entirely identical conditions as used for the OL3_{R2.7} simulations. ^eExperimental data are taken from refs 32–35.

time, provides even slightly lower *thermodynamic* stability (higher $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$) than the basic OL3 (Table 3). It is a clear indication that the HRM introduced in ref.⁶¹ may over-stabilize some potentially spurious structures in the un(mis)folded ensemble, most likely via the modified $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions.

Additional Simulations with DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} ffs. The obtained data motivated us to perform additional simulations with DES-Amber and OL3_{R2.7} RNA ffs. See the Supporting Information for a full description of all these simulations.

Results from both standard MD and ST-MetaD simulations demonstrate that the DES-Amber *ff* is improved over its DESRES predecessor for the UUCG TL. It was shown in the original papers that both ffs provide in general good results for small RNA model systems.^{44,72} However, independent testing revealed that DESRES⁴⁴ *ff* struggles with some folded RNAs with tertiary interactions, namely, it collapsed structures of RNA kink-turn 7 (Kt-7) and L1 stalk rRNA (L1-stalk rRNA).¹⁸ Loss of the Kt-7 motif was also reported for the PAK *ff* (L1-stalk rRNA was not tested).¹⁸

Our evaluation of the DES-Amber *ff* gives the following picture. The DES-Amber *ff* still struggles with the kink-turn, as it has problems with the key A-minor tertiary interaction between the stems of the kink-turn (Figure S19 in the Supporting Information). The simulations appear to ultimately lead to kink-turn unfolding and rearrangement into essentially an A-RNA-like structure with changed base pairing (Figure S20 in Supporting Information). However, there is a visible improvement of DES-Amber *ff* over DESRES *ff* in the description of the GA base pairs in the noncanonical stem of the Kt-7, and the loss of the kinked structure is considerably slower compared to the DESRES *ff*. On the other hand, for the L1-stalk rRNA, the DES-Amber *ff* provides essentially the same results as DESRES *ff*, i.e., a swift collapse of the folded structure on ~ 500 ns time scale (Figure S21 in Supporting Information), indicating persisting problems with RNA tertiary interactions. Note that a recent study reported possible problems of the DES-Amber *ff* in description of the catalytic center of the Hairpin ribozyme.¹²³

We then tested the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* (and other OL3-HRM setups; see the Supporting Information)⁶¹ on several NA systems. For canonical A-RNA the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* caused a moderate reduction of the A-RNA inclination and roll (Tables S4 and S5 in Supporting Information). The OL3_{R2.7} *ff* did not improve the simulated ensembles of RNA tetranucleotides compared to standard OL3, i.e., it resulted in considerable sampling of spurious intercalated RNA structures (see the Supporting Information for details).^{15,18,39,40,45} The OL3_{R2.7} *ff* further deepened the overcompaction of rU₅ ssRNA compared to standard OL3 (Figure S22 in Supporting Information). Note that ssRNAs such as rU₅ are known to be (severely) overcompacted when using the OL3 *ff*.^{26,124} Thus, ssRNA-specific staxif *ff* modification has been parametrized to enable stable simulations of ssRNA/protein complexes.²⁶ The compaction of rU₅ by OL3_{R2.7} *ff* indicates that some additional imbalances are introduced by the HRM, likely due to sampling of overstabilized $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions. This was ultimately confirmed by simulations of guanine quadruplexes (GQs). When simulating the Human Telomeric RNA (TERRA) GQ 3IBK¹²⁵ with UUA propeller loops we observed formation of spurious $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions between the loop backbone and the GQ stem (Figures S23–S25 in Supporting Information). Since the HRM should, in principle, be

transferable also to the DNA ffs, we have further simulated analogous Human Telomeric (Htel) DNA GQ 1KF1¹²⁶ with TTA propeller loop, combining HRM with the OL21¹²⁷ DNA *ff*. The formation of spurious $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions was even more visible for DNA GQ and some such interactions occurred even within the GQ stem (Figures S26–S29 in the Supporting Information). We also tested a “softer” version of the HRM using $R_{i,j}$ value of 2.8 \AA ⁶¹ for both RNA and DNA GQs (see Supporting Information for details), but the results remained virtually unchanged. In summary, the data indicate that while the HRM can ease steric constrictions in tightly packed parts of RNA structures, it can also lead to formation of networks of spurious $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions (H-bonds) in parts of RNA (and DNA) that have sufficient conformational freedom.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

We provide a comprehensive assessment of contemporary RNA force fields (ffs) primarily using the challenging UUCG tetraloop (TL) RNA system.

Our study employs standard brute-force molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the UUCG TL folded state to evaluate how well the ffs reproduce its native structure. Additionally, enhanced sampling folding simulations allow us to examine whether the ffs can accurately predict the $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ free energies. As our results are based primarily on one specific RNA motif, our objective was not to declare a single “best” RNA *ff*. Even with the UUCG TL system, the ranking of ffs differs depending on whether the evaluation is based on standard simulations of the folded state or on folding simulations from the unfolded state. The data indicate that rigorous testing of RNA ffs is a complex task that cannot be adequately addressed through a few anecdotal simulations or without an in-depth analysis of the trajectories.^{15,18} In the future, we plan systematic tests of diverse ffs using additional benchmark systems, namely folded RNA structures with common tertiary interactions and protein-RNA complexes.¹²⁸ We also acknowledge that we were unable to comprehensively test all RNA ffs currently available in the literature (see, e.g.,^{129–131}). However, any other RNA *ff* can be straightforwardly tested by using the set of benchmark systems and calculations presented in this paper.

Most of the tested pair-additive and both polarizable ffs did not maintain the native structure of the UUCG TL. Intriguingly, we identified three recent pair-additive *ff* variants, i.e., OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21,⁵⁶ DES-Amber⁷² and OL3_{R2.7},⁶¹ which provided fully stable native conformation of the 2KOC 14-mer UUCG TL³⁶ in $10 \times 20 \mu\text{s}$ simulations. We subsequently tested these ffs in folding simulations of the 8-mer UUCG TL and obtained strikingly variable results. While OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21 predicted folding free energy quite consistent with experimental data, the DES-Amber and especially OL3_{R2.7} *ff* variants provided higher $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ values.

The good performance of OL3_{CP}-gHBfix21 was not unexpected given its machine learning-based development and inclusion of the UUCG TL in its training set.⁵⁶ This *ff* has also been tested on a set of other RNA systems and so far no adverse effects of the gHBfix21 modification were found.⁵³ However, it does not mean that problems will not emerge in the future for insofar untested systems. The DES-Amber *ff* shows an improvement over its DESRES⁴⁴ predecessor in both standard and folding simulations of the UUCG TLs. However, it has persistent issues¹⁸ with the correct description of RNA

kink-turn and L1-stalk rRNA systems, indicating imbalances in the description of RNA tertiary interactions and some bias toward the A-RNA conformation (see [Supporting Information](#) for details). The trickiest was the analysis of the very recent OL3_{R2.7} *ff*. It introduces a substantial reduction of LJ repulsion for numerous $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ atom pairs using the NBfix approach⁷⁰ (Hydrogen Repulsion Modification; HRM)^{61,132} for the standard AMBER OL3 *ff*. It is based on an empirical observation that the compact folded stem-loop motifs contain multiple *very close* $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ contacts which, when described by standard AMBER nonbonded parameters,²⁸ lead to steric clashes (i.e., the *ff* hydrogens are “too large”).^{19,47,61} In addition, such close $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions are omnipresent in NA crystal structures.⁶¹ Indeed, the OL3_{R2.7} *ff* variant, which universally reduces the respective nonpolar $\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ R_{ij} LJ parameters to 2.7 Å, neatly corrected standard simulations of the UUCG TL. However, the HRM did not improve the predicted UUCG TL $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{fold}}$ value compared to the standard OL3 *ff*. More importantly, the HRM can lead to the formation of networks of spurious $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ interactions in parts of RNA (and DNA) molecules that have sufficient conformational freedom (See [Supporting Information](#) for details).

The present results fully expose the difficulties in the parametrization of RNA *ffs*. The HRM is based on very solid experimental and quantum chemical evidence.⁶¹ It works well for the folded UUCG TL, consistent with findings of the original study,⁶¹ as some $-\text{CH}\cdots\text{O}-$ clashes indeed arise when the standard LJ parameters²⁸ are applied. In fact, we previously identified these clashes and performed tests on the UUCG TL using reduced vdW radii of nonpolar hydrogens.⁴⁷ Subsequently, we introduced a general NBfix correction for the intranucleotide OBP interaction,⁷¹ i.e., for the $-\text{H8}\cdots\text{O5}'-$ and $-\text{H6}\cdots\text{O5}'-$ atom pairs.¹⁹ In this correction, we opted for a conservative tuning of parameters to avoid potential negative effects on other RNA and DNA systems.¹⁹ Our present simulations show that, although the HRM⁶¹ has positive effects on the folded UUCG TL, it does not improve the description of the UUCG TL folding process and may even lead to issues when transferred to other systems.

What is the primary cause of limited transferability of HRM is presently not clear and will be further investigated. It could be due to the fundamental approximation of the basic LJ potential plus atom-centered point charge model utilized by the contemporary pair-additive *ffs*, which affects especially the short-range repulsion region of the molecular interactions.^{133,134} It limits the direct transferability of quantum-chemical calculations of molecular interactions into *ff* modifications.

In this context, the advantage of the basic OL3 *ff* is that it is not overparametrized in favor of specific systems and it describes a relatively broad range of RNAs reasonably well. OL3 includes two key corrections to the original AMBER *ff*. The χ_{OL3} refinement³¹ prevents formation of spurious RNA ladder-like structures^{135,136} which would otherwise constitute the global RNA structure minimum. The bsc0 α/γ refinement³⁰ prevents occurrence of spurious γ -*trans* backbone states in A-RNA duplexes. Although the α/γ *trans/trans* states would not be dominantly populated without the bsc0 correction, they could be relatively long-living (dozens on ns) and reduce the A-RNA helical twist.¹³⁷

The present data demonstrate that the introduction of any new RNA *ff* should ideally be accompanied by tests on a diverse set of RNA motifs, including single strands

(tetranucleotides, hexanucleotides), tetraloops, A-RNA duplexes, kink-turn motifs, L1-stalk rRNA, and, where possible, other systems. Such testing would help evaluate how well the *ff* captures RNA structural dynamics across a broad spectrum of systems, highlighting its specific strengths and limitations. Given the inherent simplicity of the *ff* formalism, we remain skeptical that it is feasible to develop a universally accurate RNA *ff*. The drastic reduction of van der Waals interactions that we recently had to implement for simulations involving protein-ssRNA complexes^{26,27} and opening-closing dynamics of DNA Holliday junction¹³⁸ suggests that the complexity of NA structures, interactions, and dynamics is too vast to be comprehensively captured by a single *ff* variant. In the absence of a universal RNA *ff*, it can be justifiable to adapt atomistic *ffs* in a system-specific or goal-specific manner, even at the expense of full transferability, to address particular simulation challenges. There are certainly RNA systems that cannot be stably simulated by current *ffs*, even with system-specific adjustments, such as the molecular complex of the RRM-RGG domain of the fused in sarcoma (FUS) protein with RNA hairpin loops.²³ Perhaps, future developments in polarizable (and machine learning) *ffs* may offer greater flexibility in parametrization, potentially allowing for a single *ff* variant to capture a broader range of RNA structural dynamics. However, current evidence, including the present results and other recent studies,^{139–146} suggests that achieving the right balance in polarizable (and machine learning) NA *ffs* remains a formidable challenge.

Despite conducting nearly 4 ms of simulations, our study is far from exhaustive. We did not examine the effects of different water models in detail. Additionally, as noted by one of the Reviewers, the structural dynamics and folding of RNA are frequently influenced by both outer-shell and, at times, inner-shell interactions with Mg^{2+} ions.^{9,147,148} In addition, unbound (diffuse) Mg^{2+} ions also contribute to RNA folding. The inclusion of Mg^{2+} ions in RNA MD simulations, however, poses specific challenges. First, it inevitably increases the sampling requirements due to the slow exchange rate of ligands in the ion's primary coordination shell.⁹ The ergodicity problem is further exemplified by the use of small simulation boxes, leading to a small number of the included divalent ions, lack of bulk background ion atmosphere, etc.^{6,9,149} Moreover, experimental structural data on bound Mg^{2+} ions are often ambiguous.^{9,150} Most importantly, the high charge density of Mg^{2+} ions, along with their strong context-dependent polarizing effects, makes accurate modeling difficult,^{9,147,148} as demonstrated by quantum chemical studies.^{148,151,152} These considerations have led us to recommend avoiding Mg^{2+} ions in RNA simulations (unless the Mg^{2+} binding site is unambiguously known), as their inclusion can often introduce more complications than benefits.⁹ Several Mg^{2+} parametrizations for NA simulations with pair-additive *ffs* have been developed and reported in the literature.^{153–160} These parametrizations vary, potentially favoring different binding patterns to distinct binding sites in RNA and protein/RNA complexes;^{153–160} thus the parametrizations have to be coupled with the solute and water *ffs*. For example, we illustrated these effects in microsecond-scale simulations of the quaternary HutP homohexameric complex with mRNA, L-histidine ligand, and Mg^{2+} .¹⁶¹ Nevertheless, we believe that the principal limitation in contemporary MD simulations is the fundamental approximation of pair-additive *ffs*, which model Mg^{2+} ions as rigid LJ spheres with centrally positioned fixed

charges.^{9,147,148,152,159} We note that all reference experiments with the UUCG TL used in this study were conducted in the absence of Mg²⁺ ions.

In conclusion, while there have been significant advancements in RNA *ff* development, substantial hurdles still persist in achieving fully reliable and accurate modeling of the diverse structural dynamics of RNA systems.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

Precalculated MD data sets and NMR signals for UUCG TL are available at the URL: <https://ida.4sims.eu>.

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.4c01357>.

Details about simulations of additional systems, supporting tables, and figures in the article (PDF)

Coordinates of the identified most common misfolded states of UUCG TL and examples of key sampled structural states of RNA and DNA GQs (ZIP)

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Notes

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■ REFERENCES

- (1) Varani, G.; Nagai, K. RNA recognition by RNP proteins during RNA processing. *Annu. Rev. Biophys. Biomol. Struct.* **1998**, *27*, 407–445.
- (2) Hogg, J. R.; Collins, K. Structured non-coding RNAs and the RNP Renaissance. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2008**, *12* (6), 684–689.
- (3) Clery, A.; Blatter, M.; Allain, F. H. RNA recognition motifs: boring? *Not quite.* *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **2008**, *18* (3), 290–298.
- (4) Anko, M. L.; Neugebauer, K. M. RNA-protein interactions in vivo: global gets specific. *Trends Biochem. Sci.* **2012**, *37* (7), 255–262.
- (5) Corley, M.; Burns, M. C.; Yeo, G. W. How RNA-Binding Proteins Interact with RNA: Molecules and Mechanisms. *Mol. Cell* **2020**, *78* (1), 9–29.
- (6) Vangaveti, S.; Ranganathan, S. V.; Chen, A. A. Advances in RNA molecular dynamics: a simulator's guide to RNA force fields. *WIREs RNA* **2017**, *8* (2), No. e1396.
- (7) Smith, L. G.; Zhao, J.; Mathews, D. H.; Turner, D. H. Physics-based all-atom modeling of RNA energetics and structure. *WIREs RNA* **2017**, *8* (5), No. e1422.
- (8) Sponer, J.; Krepl, M.; Banas, P.; Kuhrova, P.; Zgarbova, M.; Jurecka, P.; Havrila, M.; Otyepka, M. How to understand atomistic molecular dynamics simulations of RNA and protein-RNA complexes? *WIREs RNA* **2017**, *8* (3), No. e1405.
- (9) Sponer, J.; Bussi, G.; Krepl, M.; Banas, P.; Bottaro, S.; Cunha, R. A.; Gil-Ley, A.; Pinamonti, G.; Poblete, S.; Jurecka, P.; et al. RNA Structural Dynamics As Captured by Molecular Simulations: A Comprehensive Overview. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118* (8), 4177–4338.
- (10) Palermo, G.; Casalino, L.; Magistrato, A.; Andrew McCammon, J. Understanding the mechanistic basis of non-coding RNA through molecular dynamics simulations. *J. Struct. Biol.* **2019**, *206* (3), 267–279.
- (11) Paloncova, M.; Pykal, M.; Kuhrova, P.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J.; Otyepka, M. Computer Aided Development of Nucleic Acid Applications in Nanotechnologies. *Small* **2022**, *18* (49), No. e2204408.
- (12) Muscat, S.; Martino, G.; Manigrasso, J.; Marcia, M.; De Vivo, M. On the Power and Challenges of Atomistic Molecular Dynamics

- to Investigate RNA Molecules. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2024**, *20*, 6992.
- (13) Mlynsky, V.; Bussi, G. Exploring RNA structure and dynamics through enhanced sampling simulations. *Curr. Opin Struct Biol.* **2018**, *49*, 63–71.
- (14) Spomer, J.; Banas, P.; Jurecka, P.; Zgarbova, M.; Kuhrova, P.; Havrila, M.; Krepl, M.; Stadlbauer, P.; Otyepka, M. Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Nucleic Acids. From Tetranucleotides to the Ribosome. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, *5* (10), 1771–1782.
- (15) Bergonzo, C.; Henriksen, N. M.; Roe, D. R.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. Highly sampled tetranucleotide and tetraloop motifs enable evaluation of common RNA force fields. *RNA* **2015**, *21* (9), 1578–1590.
- (16) Kuhrova, P.; Best, R. B.; Bottaro, S.; Bussi, G.; Spomer, J.; Otyepka, M.; Banas, P. Computer Folding of RNA Tetraloops: Identification of Key Force Field Deficiencies. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2016**, *12* (9), 4534–4548.
- (17) Nerenberg, P. S.; Head-Gordon, T. New developments in force fields for biomolecular simulations. *Curr. Opin Struct Biol.* **2018**, *49*, 129–138.
- (18) Kuhrova, P.; Mlynsky, V.; Zgarbova, M.; Krepl, M.; Bussi, G.; Best, R. B.; Otyepka, M.; Spomer, J.; Banas, P. Improving the Performance of the Amber RNA Force Field by Tuning the Hydrogen-Bonding Interactions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2019**, *15* (5), 3288–3305.
- (19) Mlynsky, V.; Kuhrova, P.; Stadlbauer, P.; Krepl, M.; Otyepka, M.; Banas, P.; Spomer, J. Simple Adjustment of Intranucleotide Base-Phosphate Interaction in the OL3 AMBER Force Field Improves RNA Simulations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2023**, *19* (22), 8423–8433.
- (20) Liebl, K.; Zacharias, M. The development of nucleic acids force fields: From an unchallenged past to a competitive future. *Biophys. J.* **2023**, *122* (14), 2841–2851.
- (21) Love, O.; Winkler, L.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. van der Waals Parameter Scanning with Amber Nucleic Acid Force Fields: Revisiting Means to Better Capture the RNA/DNA Structure through MD. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2024**, *20* (2), 625–643.
- (22) Choi, T.; Li, Z.; Song, G.; Chen, H. F. Comprehensive Comparison and Critical Assessment of RNA-Specific Force Fields. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2024**, *20* (6), 2676–2688.
- (23) Pokorna, P.; Krepl, M.; Campagne, S.; Spomer, J. Conformational Heterogeneity of RNA Stem-Loop Hairpins Bound to FUS-RNA Recognition Motif with Disordered RGG Tail Revealed by Unbiased Molecular Dynamics Simulations. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2022**, *126* (45), 9207–9221.
- (24) Berman, H. M.; Westbrook, J.; Feng, Z.; Gilliland, G.; Bhat, T. N.; Weissig, H.; Shindyalov, I. N.; Bourne, P. E. The Protein Data Bank. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2000**, *28* (1), 235–242.
- (25) Ripin, N.; Boudet, J.; Duszczak, M. M.; Hinniger, A.; Faller, M.; Krepl, M.; Gadi, A.; Schneider, R. J.; Spomer, J.; Meisner-Kober, N. C.; et al. Molecular basis for AU-rich element recognition and dimerization by the HuR C-terminal RRM. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2019**, *116* (8), 2935–2944.
- (26) Krepl, M.; Pokorna, P.; Mlynsky, V.; Stadlbauer, P.; Spomer, J. Spontaneous binding of single-stranded RNAs to RRM proteins visualized by unbiased atomistic simulations with a rescaled RNA force field. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2022**, *50* (21), 12480–12496.
- (27) Lemmens, T.; Spomer, J.; Krepl, M. How Binding Site Flexibility Promotes RNA Scanning in TbRGG2 RRM: A Molecular Dynamics Simulation Study. *bioRxiv* **2024**, DOI: 10.1101/2024.09.25.614920.
- (28) Cornell, W. D.; Cieplak, P.; Bayly, C. I.; Gould, I. R.; Merz, K. M.; Ferguson, D. M.; Spellmeyer, D. C.; Fox, T.; Caldwell, J. W.; Kollman, P. A. A second generation force field for the simulation of proteins, nucleic acids, and organic molecules (vol 117, pg 5179, 1995). *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1996**, *118* (9), 2309–2309.
- (29) Wang, J. M.; Cieplak, P.; Kollman, P. A. How well does a restrained electrostatic potential (RESP) model perform in calculating conformational energies of organic and biological molecules? *J. Comput. Chem.* **2000**, *21* (12), 1049–1074.
- (30) Perez, A.; Marchan, I.; Svozil, D.; Spomer, J.; Cheatham, T. E.; Laughton, C. A. Orozco, M. Refinement of the AMBER Force Field for Nucleic Acids: Improving the Description of Alpha/Gamma Conformers. *Biophys. J.* **2007**, *92* (11), 3817–3829.
- (31) Zgarbova, M.; Otyepka, M.; Spomer, J.; Mladek, A.; Banas, P.; Cheatham, T. E.; Jurecka, P. Refinement of the Cornell et al. Nucleic Acids Force Field Based on Reference Quantum Chemical Calculations of Glycosidic Torsion Profiles. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2011**, *7* (9), 2886–2902.
- (32) Molinaro, M.; Tinoco, I., Jr. Use of ultra stable UNCG tetraloop hairpins to fold RNA structures: thermodynamic and spectroscopic applications. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **1995**, *23* (15), 3056–3063.
- (33) Abdelkafi, M.; Ghomi, M.; Turpin, P. Y.; Baumruk, V.; Herve du Penhoat, C.; Lampire, O.; Bouchemal-Chibani, N.; Goyer, P.; Namane, A.; Gouyette, C.; et al. Common structural features of UUCG and UACG tetraloops in very short hairpins determined by UV absorption, Raman, IR and NMR spectroscopies. *J. Biomol. Struct. Dyn.* **1997**, *14* (5), 579–593.
- (34) Mathews, D. H.; Disney, M. D.; Childs, J. L.; Schroeder, S. J.; Zuker, M.; Turner, D. H. Incorporating chemical modification constraints into a dynamic programming algorithm for prediction of RNA secondary structure. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2004**, *101* (19), 7287–7292.
- (35) Proctor, D. J.; Ma, H.; Kierzek, E.; Kierzek, R.; Gruebele, M.; Bevilacqua, P. C. Folding thermodynamics and kinetics of YNMG RNA hairpins: specific incorporation of 8-bromoguanosine leads to stabilization by enhancement of the folding rate. *Biochemistry* **2004**, *43* (44), 14004–14014.
- (36) Nozinovic, S.; Furtig, B.; Jonker, H. R.; Richter, C.; Schwalbe, H. High-resolution NMR structure of an RNA model system: the 14-mer cUUCGg tetraloop hairpin RNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2010**, *38* (2), 683–694.
- (37) Yildirim, I.; Stern, H. A.; Tubbs, J. D.; Kennedy, S. D.; Turner, D. H. Benchmarking AMBER force fields for RNA: comparisons to NMR spectra for single-stranded r(GACC) are improved by revised chi torsions. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2011**, *115* (29), 9261–9270.
- (38) Tubbs, J. D.; Condon, D. E.; Kennedy, S. D.; Hauser, M.; Bevilacqua, P. C.; Turner, D. H. The nuclear magnetic resonance of CCCC RNA reveals a right-handed helix, and revised parameters for AMBER force field torsions improve structural predictions from molecular dynamics. *Biochemistry* **2013**, *52* (6), 996–1010.
- (39) Condon, D. E.; Kennedy, S. D.; Mort, B. C.; Kierzek, R.; Yildirim, I.; Turner, D. H. Stacking in RNA: NMR of Four Tetramers Benchmark Molecular Dynamics. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2015**, *11* (6), 2729–2742.
- (40) Bergonzo, C.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. Improved Force Field Parameters Lead to a Better Description of RNA Structure. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2015**, *11* (9), 3969–3972.
- (41) Bottaro, S.; Banas, P.; Spomer, J.; Bussi, G. Free Energy Landscape of GAGA and UUCG RNA Tetraloops. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2016**, *7* (20), 4032–4038.
- (42) Cesari, A.; Gil-Ley, A.; Bussi, G. Combining Simulations and Solution Experiments as a Paradigm for RNA Force Field Refinement. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2016**, *12* (12), 6192–6200.
- (43) Aytenfisu, A. H.; Spasic, A.; Grossfield, A.; Stern, H. A.; Mathews, D. H. Revised RNA Dihedral Parameters for the Amber Force Field Improve RNA Molecular Dynamics. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2017**, *13* (2), 900–915.
- (44) Tan, D.; Piana, S.; Dirks, R. M.; Shaw, D. E. RNA force field with accuracy comparable to state-of-the-art protein force fields. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2018**, *115* (7), E1346–E1355.
- (45) Bottaro, S.; Bussi, G.; Kennedy, S. D.; Turner, D. H.; Lindorff-Larsen, K. Conformational ensembles of RNA oligonucleotides from integrating NMR and molecular simulations. *Sci. Adv.* **2018**, *4* (5), No. eaar8521.

- (46) Cesari, A.; Bottaro, S.; Lindorff-Larsen, K.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J.; Bussi, G. Fitting Corrections to an RNA Force Field Using Experimental Data. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2019**, *15* (6), 3425–3431.
- (47) Mrazikova, K.; Mlynsky, V.; Kuhrova, P.; Pokorna, P.; Kruse, H.; Krepl, M.; Otyepka, M.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J. UUCG RNA Tetraloop as a Formidable Force-Field Challenge for MD Simulations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2020**, *16* (12), 7601–7617.
- (48) Mlynsky, V.; Kuhrova, P.; Kuhr, T.; Otyepka, M.; Bussi, G.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J. Fine-Tuning of the AMBER RNA Force Field with a New Term Adjusting Interactions of Terminal Nucleotides. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2020**, *16* (6), 3936–3946.
- (49) Zhao, J.; Kennedy, S. D.; Berger, K. D.; Turner, D. H. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance of Single-Stranded RNAs and DNAs of CAAU and UCAAUC as Benchmarks for Molecular Dynamics Simulations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2020**, *16* (3), 1968–1984.
- (50) Bottaro, S.; Nichols, P. J.; Vogeli, B.; Parrinello, M.; Lindorff-Larsen, K. Integrating NMR and simulations reveals motions in the UUCG tetraloop. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2020**, *48* (11), 5839–5848.
- (51) Frohliking, T.; Bernetti, M.; Calonaci, N.; Bussi, G. Toward empirical force fields that match experimental observables. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *152* (23), No. 230902.
- (52) Reisser, S.; Zucchelli, S.; Gustincich, S.; Bussi, G. Conformational ensembles of an RNA hairpin using molecular dynamics and sparse NMR data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2020**, *48* (3), 1164–1174.
- (53) Zerze, G. H.; Piaggi, P. M.; Debenedetti, P. G. A Computational Study of RNA Tetraloop Thermodynamics, Including Misfolded States. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2021**, *125* (50), 13685–13695.
- (54) Zhao, J.; Kennedy, S. D.; Turner, D. H. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra and AMBER OL3 and ROC-RNA Simulations of UCUCGU Reveal Force Field Strengths and Weaknesses for Single-Stranded RNA. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2022**, *18* (2), 1241–1254.
- (55) Bergonzo, C.; Grishaev, A.; Bottaro, S. Conformational heterogeneity of UCAAUC RNA oligonucleotide from molecular dynamics simulations, SAXS, and NMR experiments. *RNA* **2022**, *28* (7), 937–946.
- (56) Frohliking, T.; Mlynsky, V.; Janecek, M.; Kuhrova, P.; Krepl, M.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J.; Bussi, G. Automatic Learning of Hydrogen-Bond Fixes in the AMBER RNA Force Field. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2022**, *18* (7), 4490–4502.
- (57) Ennifar, E.; Nikulin, A.; Tishchenko, S.; Serganov, A.; Nevskaya, N.; Garber, M.; Ehresmann, B.; Ehresmann, C.; Nikonov, S.; Dumas, P. The crystal structure of UUCG tetraloop. *J. Mol. Biol.* **2000**, *304* (1), 35–42.
- (58) Carter, A. P.; Clemons, W. M.; Brodersen, D. E.; Morgan-Warren, R. J.; Wimberly, B. T.; Ramakrishnan, V. Functional insights from the structure of the 30S ribosomal subunit and its interactions with antibiotics. *Nature* **2000**, *407* (6802), 340–348.
- (59) Tishchenko, S.; Nikulin, A.; Fomenkova, N.; Nevskaya, N.; Nikonov, O.; Dumas, P.; Moine, H.; Ehresmann, B.; Ehresmann, C.; Piendl, W.; et al. Detailed analysis of RNA-protein interactions within the ribosomal protein S8-rRNA complex from the archaeon *Methanococcus jannaschii*. *J. Mol. Biol.* **2001**, *311* (2), 311–324.
- (60) Zhang, C.; Lu, C.; Jing, Z.; Wu, C.; Piquemal, J. P.; Ponder, J. W.; Ren, P. AMOEBA Polarizable Atomic Multipole Force Field for Nucleic Acids. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2018**, *14* (4), 2084–2108.
- (61) Raguette, L. E.; Gunasekera, S. S.; Diaz Ventura, R. I.; Aminov, E.; Linzer, J. T.; Parwana, D.; Wu, Q.; Simmerling, C.; Nagan, M. C. Adjusting the Energy Profile for CH-O Interactions Leads to Improved Stability of RNA Stem-Loop Structures in MD Simulations. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2024**, *128* (33), 7921–7933.
- (62) Yang, C.; Lim, M.; Kim, E.; Pak, Y. Predicting RNA Structures via a Simple van der Waals Correction to an All-Atom Force Field. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2017**, *13* (2), 395–399.
- (63) Mlynsky, V.; Janecek, M.; Kuhrova, P.; Frohliking, T.; Otyepka, M.; Bussi, G.; Banas, P.; Sponer, J. Toward Convergence in Folding Simulations of RNA Tetraloops: Comparison of Enhanced Sampling Techniques and Effects of Force Field Modifications. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2022**, *18* (4), 2642–2656.
- (64) Nissen, P.; Ippolito, J. A.; Ban, N.; Moore, P. B.; Steitz, T. A. RNA tertiary interactions in the large ribosomal subunit: the A-minor motif. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2001**, *98* (9), 4899–4903.
- (65) Tamura, M.; Holbrook, S. R. Sequence and structural conservation in RNA ribose zippers. *J. Mol. Biol.* **2002**, *320* (3), 455–474.
- (66) Mokdad, A.; Krasovska, M. V.; Sponer, J.; Leontis, N. B. Structural and evolutionary classification of G/U wobble basepairs in the ribosome. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2006**, *34* (5), 1326–1341.
- (67) *Amber 2024*; University of California: San Francisco, 2024.
- (68) Steinbrecher, T.; Latzer, J.; Case, D. A. Revised AMBER Parameters for Bioorganic Phosphates. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2012**, *8* (11), 4405–4412.
- (69) Mlynsky, V.; Kuhrova, P.; Zgarbova, M.; Jurecka, P.; Walter, N. G.; Otyepka, M.; Sponer, J.; Banas, P. Reactive conformation of the active site in the hairpin ribozyme achieved by molecular dynamics simulations with epsilon/zeta force field reparametrizations. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2015**, *119* (11), 4220–4229.
- (70) Yoo, J.; Aksimentiev, A. New tricks for old dogs: improving the accuracy of biomolecular force fields by pair-specific corrections to non-bonded interactions. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2018**, *20* (13), 8432–8449.
- (71) Zirbel, C. L.; Sponer, J. E.; Sponer, J.; Stombaugh, J.; Leontis, N. B. Classification and energetics of the base-phosphate interactions in RNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2009**, *37* (15), 4898–4918.
- (72) Tucker, M. R.; Piana, S.; Tan, D.; LeVine, M. V.; Shaw, D. E. Development of Force Field Parameters for the Simulation of Single- and Double-Stranded DNA Molecules and DNA-Protein Complexes. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2022**, *126* (24), 4442–4457.
- (73) Chen, A. A.; Garcia, A. E. High-resolution reversible folding of hyperstable RNA tetraloops using molecular dynamics simulations. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2013**, *110* (42), 16820–16825.
- (74) Chen, J.; Liu, H.; Cui, X.; Li, Z.; Chen, H. F. RNA-Specific Force Field Optimization with CMAP and Reweighting. *J. Chem. Inf Model* **2022**, *62* (2), 372–385.
- (75) Li, Z.; Mu, J.; Chen, J.; Chen, H. F. Base-specific RNA force field improving the dynamics conformation of nucleotide. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2022**, *222* (Pt A), 680–690.
- (76) Brooks, B. R.; Brooks, C. L., 3rd; Mackerell, A. D., Jr.; Nilsson, L.; Petrella, R. J.; Roux, B.; Won, Y.; Archontis, G.; Bartels, C.; Boresch, S.; et al. CHARMM: the biomolecular simulation program. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2009**, *30* (10), 1545–1614.
- (77) Denning, E. J.; Priyakumar, U. D.; Nilsson, L.; Mackerell, A. D. Impact of 2'-Hydroxyl Sampling on the Conformational Properties of RNA: Update of the CHARMM All-Atom Additive Force Field for RNA. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2011**, *32* (9), 1929–1943.
- (78) Izadi, S.; Anandakrishnan, R.; Onufriev, A. V. Building Water Models: A Different Approach. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, *5* (21), 3863–3871.
- (79) Piana, S.; Donchev, A. G.; Robustelli, P.; Shaw, D. E. Water Dispersion Interactions Strongly Influence Simulated Structural Properties of Disordered Protein States. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2015**, *119* (16), 5113–5123.
- (80) Jorgensen, W. L.; Chandrasekhar, J.; Madura, J. D.; Impey, R. W.; Klein, M. L. Comparison of Simple Potential Functions for Simulating Liquid Water. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1983**, *79* (2), 926–935.
- (81) Joung, I. S.; Cheatham, T. E. Determination of alkali and halide monovalent ion parameters for use in explicitly solvated biomolecular simulations. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2008**, *112* (30), 9020–9041.
- (82) Kuhrova, P.; Mlynsky, V.; Zgarbova, M.; Krepl, M.; Bussi, G.; Best, R. B.; Otyepka, M.; Sponer, J.; Banas, P. Correction to "Improving the Performance of the Amber RNA Force Field by Tuning the Hydrogen-Bonding Interactions". *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2020**, *16* (1), 818–819.
- (83) MacKerell, A. D.; Bashford, D.; Bellott, M.; Dunbrack, R. L.; Evanseck, J. D.; Field, M. J.; Fischer, S.; Gao, J.; Guo, H.; Ha, S.; et al. All-atom empirical potential for molecular modeling and dynamics studies of proteins. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1998**, *102* (18), 3586–3616.

- (84) Chen, A. A.; Pappu, R. V. Parameters of monovalent ions in the AMBER-99 forcefield: assessment of inaccuracies and proposed improvements. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2007**, *111* (41), 11884–11887.
- (85) Sengupta, A.; Li, Z.; Song, L. F.; Li, P.; Merz, K. M., Jr. Parameterization of Monovalent Ions for the OPC3, OPC, TIP3P-FB, and TIP4P-FB Water Models. *J. Chem. Inf Model* **2021**, *61* (2), 869–880.
- (86) Case, D. A.; Ben-Shalom, I. Y.; Brozell, S. R.; Cerutti, D. S.; Cheatham, I. T. E.; Cruzeiro, V. W. D.; Darden, T. A.; Duke, R. E.; Ghoreishi, D.; Gilson, M. K. *AMBER 2018*; University of California: San Francisco, 2018.
- (87) Le Grand, S.; Goetz, A. W.; Walker, R. C. SPFP: Speed Without Compromise - A Mixed Precision Model for GPU Accelerated Molecular Dynamics Simulations. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **2013**, *184* (2), 374–380.
- (88) Hopkins, C. W.; Le Grand, S.; Walker, R. C.; Roitberg, A. E. Long-Time-Step Molecular Dynamics through Hydrogen Mass Repartitioning. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2015**, *11* (4), 1864–1874.
- (89) Darden, T.; York, D.; Pedersen, L. Particle Mesh Ewald - An $N \log(N)$ Method for Ewald Sums in Large Systems. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98* (12), 10089–10092.
- (90) Parisi, G. Correlation functions and computer simulations. *Nuclear Physics B* **1981**, *180* (3), 378–384.
- (91) Abraham, M. J.; Murtola, T.; Schulz, R.; Páll, S.; Smith, J. C.; Hess, B.; Lindahl, E. GROMACS: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers. *SoftwareX* **2015**, *1*, 19–25.
- (92) Hess, B.; Bekker, H.; Berendsen, H. J. C.; Fraaije, J. G. E. M. LINCS: A Linear Constraint Solver for Molecular Simulations. *J. Comput. Chem.* **1997**, *18* (12), 1463–1472.
- (93) Bussi, G.; Donadio, D.; Parrinello, M. Canonical Sampling through Velocity Rescaling. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2007**, *126* (1), No. 014101.
- (94) Savelyev, A.; MacKerell, A. D., Jr. All-atom polarizable force field for DNA based on the classical Drude oscillator model. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2014**, *35* (16), 1219–1239.
- (95) Lemkul, J. A.; MacKerell, A. D. Polarizable Force Field for DNA Based on the Classical Drude Oscillator: I. Refinement Using Quantum Mechanical Base Stacking and Conformational Energetics. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2017**, *13* (5), 2053–2071.
- (96) Lemkul, J. A.; MacKerell, A. D. Polarizable Force Field for DNA Based on the Classical Drude Oscillator: II. Microsecond Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Duplex DNA. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2017**, *13* (5), 2072–2085.
- (97) Lemkul, J. A.; MacKerell, A. D., Jr. Polarizable force field for RNA based on the classical drude oscillator. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2018**, *39* (32), 2624–2646.
- (98) Lamoureux, G.; Harder, E.; Vorobyov, I. V.; Roux, B.; MacKerell, A. D., Jr. A polarizable model of water for molecular dynamics simulations of biomolecules. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2006**, *418* (1–3), 245–249.
- (99) Zhang, C.; Bell, D.; Harger, M.; Ren, P. Polarizable Multipole-Based Force Field for Aromatic Molecules and Nucleobases. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2017**, *13* (2), 666–678.
- (100) Phillips, J. C.; Hardy, D. J.; Maia, J. D. C.; Stone, J. E.; Ribeiro, J. V.; Bernardi, R. C.; Buch, R.; Fiorin, G.; Henin, J.; Jiang, W.; et al. Scalable molecular dynamics on CPU and GPU architectures with NAMD. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *153* (4), No. 044130.
- (101) Eastman, P.; Swails, J.; Chodera, J. D.; McGibbon, R. T.; Zhao, Y.; Beauchamp, K. A.; Wang, L. P.; Simmonett, A. C.; Harrigan, M. P.; Stern, C. D.; et al. OpenMM 7: Rapid development of high performance algorithms for molecular dynamics. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **2017**, *13* (7), No. e1005659.
- (102) Jiang, W.; Hardy, D. J.; Phillips, J. C.; Mackerell, A. D., Jr.; Schulten, K.; Roux, B. High-performance scalable molecular dynamics simulations of a polarizable force field based on classical Drude oscillators in NAMD. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2011**, *2* (2), 87–92.
- (103) Huang, J.; Lemkul, J. A.; Eastman, P. K.; MacKerell, A. D., Jr. Molecular dynamics simulations using the drude polarizable force field on GPUs with OpenMM: Implementation, validation, and benchmarks. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2018**, *39* (21), 1682–1689.
- (104) Chow, K. H.; Ferguson, D. M. Isothermal-isobaric molecular dynamics simulations with Monte Carlo volume sampling. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **1995**, *91* (1–3), 283–289.
- (105) Ryckaert, J. P.; Ciccotti, G.; Berendsen, H. J. C. Numerical Integration of Cartesian Equations of Motion of a System with Constraints - Molecular Dynamics of N-alkans. *J. Comput. Phys.* **1977**, *23* (3), 327–341.
- (106) Miyamoto, S.; Kollman, P. A. Settle: An Analytical Version of the SHAKE and RATTLE Algorithm for Rigid Water Models. *J. Comput. Chem.* **1992**, *13* (8), 952–962.
- (107) Essmann, U.; Perera, L.; Berkowitz, M. L.; Darden, T.; Lee, H.; Pedersen, L. G. A smooth particle mesh Ewald method. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1995**, *103* (19), 8577–8593.
- (108) Åqvist, J.; Wennerström, P.; Nervall, M.; Bjelic, S.; Brandsdal, B. O. Molecular dynamics simulations of water and biomolecules with a Monte Carlo constant pressure algorithm. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2004**, *384* (4–6), 288–294.
- (109) Tuckerman, M. B. B. J. M.; Berne, B. J.; Martyna, G. J. Reversible multiple time scale molecular dynamics. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1992**, *97* (3), 1990–2001.
- (110) Adjoua, O.; Lagardere, L.; Jolly, L. H.; Durocher, A.; Very, T.; Dupays, I.; Wang, Z.; Inizan, T. J.; Celerse, F.; Ren, P.; et al. Tinker-HP: Accelerating Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Large Complex Systems with Advanced Point Dipole Polarizable Force Fields Using GPUs and Multi-GPU Systems. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2021**, *17* (4), 2034–2053.
- (111) Laio, A.; Parrinello, M. Escaping free-energy minima. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2002**, *99* (20), 12562–12566.
- (112) Barducci, A.; Bussi, G.; Parrinello, M. Well-tempered metadynamics: a smoothly converging and tunable free-energy method. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2008**, *100* (2), No. 020603.
- (113) Bussi, G.; Laio, A. Using metadynamics to explore complex free-energy landscapes. *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **2020**, *2* (4), 200–212.
- (114) Wang, L.; Friesner, R. A.; Berne, B. J. Replica exchange with solute scaling: a more efficient version of replica exchange with solute tempering (REST2). *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2011**, *115* (30), 9431–9438.
- (115) Bottaro, S.; Di Palma, F.; Bussi, G. The role of nucleobase interactions in RNA structure and dynamics. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2014**, *42* (21), 13306–13314.
- (116) Tribello, G. A.; Bonomi, M.; Branduardi, D.; Camilloni, C.; Bussi, G. PLUMED 2: New feathers for an old bird. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **2014**, *185* (2), 604–613.
- (117) Bussi, G. Hamiltonian Replica Exchange in GROMACS: A Flexible Implementation. *Mol. Phys.* **2014**, *112* (3–4), 379–384.
- (118) Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K. VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *J. Mol. Graph Model* **1996**, *14* (1), 33–38.
- (119) *The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 1.8*; 2015.
- (120) Roe, D. R.; Cheatham, T. E. PTRAJ and CPPTRAJ: Software for Processing and Analysis of Molecular Dynamics Trajectory Data. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2013**, *9* (7), 3084–3095.
- (121) Leontis, N. B.; Westhof, E. Geometric Nomenclature and Classification of RNA Base Pairs. *RNA* **2001**, *7* (4), 499–512.
- (122) Sarver, M.; Zirbel, C. L.; Stombaugh, J.; Mokdad, A.; Leontis, N. B. FR3D: finding local and composite recurrent structural motifs in RNA 3D structures. *J. Math. Biol.* **2007**, *56* (1–2), 215–252.
- (123) Forget, S.; Juille, M.; Duboue-Dijon, E.; Stirnemann, G. Simulation-Guided Conformational Space Exploration to Assess Reactive Conformations of a Ribozyme. *J. Chem. Theory Comput* **2024**, *20* (14), 6263–6277.
- (124) Grotz, K. K.; Nueesch, M. F.; Holmstrom, E. D.; Heinz, M.; Stelzl, L. S.; Schuler, B.; Hummer, G. Dispersion Correction Alleviates Dye Stacking of Single-Stranded DNA and RNA in Simulations of Single-Molecule Fluorescence Experiments. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2018**, *122* (49), 11626–11639.
- (125) Collie, G. W.; Haider, S. M.; Neidle, S.; Parkinson, G. N. A crystallographic and modelling study of a human telomeric RNA (TERRA) quadruplex. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2010**, *38* (16), 5569–5580.

- (126) Parkinson, G. N.; Lee, M. P.; Neidle, S. Crystal structure of parallel quadruplexes from human telomeric DNA. *Nature* **2002**, *417* (6891), 876–880.
- (127) Zgarbová, M.; Šponer, J. i.; Jurečka, P. Z-DNA as a Touchstone for Additive Empirical Force Fields and a Refinement of the Alpha/Gamma DNA torsions for AMBER. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2021**, *17*, 6292.
- (128) Baltrukевич, H.; Bartos, P. RNA-protein complexes and force field polarizability. *Front Chem.* **2023**, *11*, No. 1217506.
- (129) Yildirim, I.; Stern, H. A.; Kennedy, S. D.; Tubbs, J. D.; Turner, D. H. Reparameterization of RNA chi Torsion Parameters for the AMBER Force Field and Comparison to NMR Spectra for Cytidine and Uridine. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2010**, *6* (5), 1520–1531.
- (130) Wales, D. J.; Yildirim, I. Improving Computational Predictions of Single-Stranded RNA Tetramers with Revised alpha/gamma Torsional Parameters for the Amber Force Field. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2017**, *121* (14), 2989–2999.
- (131) Robertson, M. J.; Qian, Y.; Robinson, M. C.; Tirado-Rives, J.; Jorgensen, W. L. Development and Testing of the OPLS-AA/M Force Field for RNA. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2019**, *15* (4), 2734–2742.
- (132) Linzer, J. T.; Aminov, E.; Abdullah, A. S.; Kirkup, C. E.; Diaz Ventura, R. I.; Bijoer, V. R.; Jung, J.; Huang, S.; Tse, C. G.; Alvarez Toucet, E.; et al. Accurately Modeling RNA Stem-Loops in an Implicit Solvent Environment. *J. Chem. Inf Model.* **2024**, *64* (15), 6092–6104.
- (133) Morgado, C. A.; Jurecka, P.; Svozil, D.; Hobza, P.; Sponer, J. Balance of Attraction and Repulsion in Nucleic-Acid Base Stacking: CCSD(T)/Complete-Basis-Set-Limit Calculations on Uracil Dimer and a Comparison with the Force-Field Description. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2009**, *5* (6), 1524–1544.
- (134) Zgarbova, M.; Otyepka, M.; Sponer, J.; Hobza, P.; Jurecka, P. Large-scale compensation of errors in pairwise-additive empirical force fields: comparison of AMBER intermolecular terms with rigorous DFT-SAPT calculations. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *12* (35), 10476–10493.
- (135) Mlynsky, V.; Banas, P.; Hollas, D.; Reblova, K.; Walter, N. G.; Sponer, J.; Otyepka, M. Extensive Molecular Dynamics Simulations Showing That Canonical G8 and Protonated A38H⁺ Forms Are Most Consistent with Crystal Structures of Hairpin Ribozyme. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2010**, *114* (19), 6642–6652.
- (136) Banas, P.; Hollas, D.; Zgarbova, M.; Jurecka, P.; Orozco, M.; Cheatham, T. E.; Sponer, J.; Otyepka, M. Performance of Molecular Mechanics Force Fields for RNA Simulations: Stability of UUCG and GNRA Hairpins. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2010**, *6* (12), 3836–3849.
- (137) Reblova, K.; Lankas, F.; Razga, F.; Krasovska, M. V.; Koca, J.; Sponer, J. Structure, dynamics, and elasticity of free 16s rRNA helix 44 studied by molecular dynamics simulations. *Biopolymers* **2006**, *82* (5), 504–520.
- (138) Zhang, Z.; Sponer, J.; Bussi, G.; Mlynsky, V.; Sulc, P.; Simmons, C. R.; Stephanopoulos, N.; Krepl, M. Atomistic Picture of Opening-Closing Dynamics of DNA Holliday Junction Obtained by Molecular Simulations. *J. Chem. Inf Model.* **2023**, *63* (9), 2794–2809.
- (139) Lemkul, J. A. Same Fold, Different Properties: Polarizable Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Telomeric and TERRA G-Quadruplexes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2020**, *48* (2), 561–575.
- (140) Salisbury, A. M.; Dean, T. J.; Lemkul, J. A. Polarizable Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Two c-kit Oncogene Promoter G-Quadruplexes: Effect of Primary and Secondary Structure on Loop and Ion Sampling. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2020**, *16* (5), 3430–3444.
- (141) Jing, Z.; Ren, P. Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Protein RNA Complexes by Using an Advanced Electrostatic Model. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2022**, *126* (38), 7343–7353.
- (142) Winkler, L.; Galindo-Murillo, R.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. Structures and Dynamics of DNA Mini-Dumbbells Are Force Field Dependent. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2023**, *19* (8), 2198–2212.
- (143) Winkler, L.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. Benchmarking the Drude Polarizable Force Field Using the r(GACC) Tetranucleotide. *J. Chem. Inf Model.* **2023**, *63* (8), 2505–2511.
- (144) Winkler, L.; Galindo-Murillo, R.; Cheatham, T. E., 3rd. Assessment of A- to B- DNA Transitions Utilizing the Drude Polarizable Force Field. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2023**, *19* (23), 8955–8966.
- (145) Knappeova, B.; Mlynsky, V.; Pykal, M.; Sponer, J.; Banas, P.; Otyepka, M.; Krepl, M. Comprehensive Assessment of Force-Field Performance in Molecular Dynamics Simulations of DNA/RNA Hybrid Duplexes. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2024**, *20* (15), 6917–6929.
- (146) Wang, Y.; Takaba, K.; Chen, M. S.; Wieder, M.; Xu, Y.; Zhu, T.; Zhang, J. Z. H.; Nagle, A.; Yu, K.; Wang, X.; et al. On the design space between molecular mechanics and machine learning force fields. *arXiv* **2024**, DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2409.01931.
- (147) Bowman, J. C.; Lenz, T. K.; Hud, N. V.; Williams, L. D. Cations in charge: magnesium ions in RNA folding and catalysis. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* **2012**, *22* (3), 262–272.
- (148) Casalino, L.; Palermo, G.; Abdurakhmonova, N.; Rothlisberger, U.; Magistrato, A. Development of Site-Specific Mg(2+)-RNA Force Field Parameters: A Dream or Reality? Guidelines from Combined Molecular Dynamics and Quantum Mechanics Simulations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2017**, *13* (1), 340–352.
- (149) Cunha, R. A.; Bussi, G. Unraveling Mg(2+)-RNA binding with atomistic molecular dynamics. *RNA* **2017**, *23* (5), 628–638.
- (150) Auffinger, P.; Ennifar, E.; D’Ascenzo, L. Deflating the RNA Mg(2+) bubble. Stereochemistry to the rescue! *RNA* **2021**, *27* (3), 243–252.
- (151) Sponer, J.; Sabat, M.; Gorb, L.; Leszczynski, J.; Lippert, B.; Hobza, P. The effect of metal binding to the N7 site of purine nucleotides on their structure, energy, and involvement in base pairing. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2000**, *104* (31), 7535–7544.
- (152) Petrov, A. S.; Bowman, J. C.; Harvey, S. C.; Williams, L. D. Bidentate RNA-magnesium clamps: on the origin of the special role of magnesium in RNA folding. *RNA* **2011**, *17* (2), 291–297.
- (153) Aqvist, J. Ion-water interaction potentials derived from free energy perturbation simulations. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1990**, *94* (21), 8021–8024.
- (154) Allner, O.; Nilsson, L.; Villa, A. Magnesium Ion-Water Coordination and Exchange in Biomolecular Simulations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2012**, *8* (4), 1493–1502.
- (155) Li, P.; Roberts, B. P.; Chakravorty, D. K.; Merz, K. M., Jr. Rational Design of Particle Mesh Ewald Compatible Lennard-Jones Parameters for + 2 Metal Cations in Explicit Solvent. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2013**, *9* (6), 2733–2748.
- (156) Li, P.; Merz, K. M., Jr. Taking into Account the Ion-induced Dipole Interaction in the Nonbonded Model of Ions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2014**, *10* (1), 289–297.
- (157) Panteva, M. T.; Giambasu, G. M.; York, D. M. Comparison of structural, thermodynamic, kinetic and mass transport properties of Mg(2+) ion models commonly used in biomolecular simulations. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2015**, *36* (13), 970–982.
- (158) Panteva, M. T.; Giambasu, G. M.; York, D. M. Force Field for Mg(2+), Mn(2+), Zn(2+), and Cd(2+) Ions That Have Balanced Interactions with Nucleic Acids. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2015**, *119* (50), 15460–15470.
- (159) Li, P.; Merz, K. M., Jr. Metal Ion Modeling Using Classical Mechanics. *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117* (3), 1564–1686.
- (160) Grotz, K. K.; Schwierz, N. Optimized Magnesium Force Field Parameters for Biomolecular Simulations with Accurate Solvation, Ion-Binding, and Water-Exchange Properties in SPC/E, TIP3P-fb, TIP4P/2005, TIP4P-Ew, and TIP4P-D. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2022**, *18* (1), 526–537.
- (161) Pokorna, P.; Krepl, M.; Kruse, H.; Sponer, J. MD and QM/MM Study of the Quaternary HutP Homohexamer Complex with mRNA, l-Histidine Ligand, and Mg²⁺. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2017**, *13* (11), 5658–5670.